

Deliverable 5.1

Design and Specification of the first ERL Smart City competition

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Deliverable author(s):	Emanuele Bastianelli, Luca Iocchi, Enrico Motta, Daniele Nardi, Ilaria Tiddi
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Content

1.	Introduction	5
1.1	Purpose of the present document	5
1.2	Overview of the present document	5
2.	From smart cities to ERL Smart Cities	6
2.1	Smart cities	6
2.2	The case of Milton Keynes as a smart city	7
2.3	Robots in smart cities	8
2.4	Relation with the other ERLs	9
2.5	Relation with the Eurobench project	10
3.	The 1st ERL Smart Cities RObotics Challenge	10
3.1	Scenario	11
3.2	Episodes	11
3.2.1	Characterisation of episodes	12
3.2.2	Categories of episodes	12
3.2.3	Episode selection process	13
3.3	Competition environment	13
3.4	Data infrastructure for the competition	14
3.5	Tentative schedule	15
4.	Specification of the competition	16
4.1	Episode 01 - Attract a customer	17
4.2	Episode 02 - Shopping Guide	18
4.3	Episode 03 - Delivering coffee shop orders	20
4.4	Episode 04 - Take the elevator	21
4.5	Episode 05 - Unattended item	22
4.6	Episode 06 - Wiping a drink poured on the floor	23
4.7	Episode 07 - Serving goodies	25
4.8	Episode 08 - At the checkout desk	26
4.9	Episode 09 - Cart push	27

4.10	Episode 10 - Open the door	29
4.11	Episode 11 - Finding a lost dog with a drone	31
4.12	Episode 12 - Fast delivery of emergency pills	32

List of acronyms

DH	MK:DataHub
DOW	Description Of Work
Eoi	Expression of Interest
ERL	European Robotic League
FBM	Functional Benchmark
MK	Milton Keynes
TBM	Task Benchmark
VTOL	Vertical take-off and landing
WP	Work Package

1. Introduction

Smart cities are a new urban innovation paradigm promoting the use of advanced technologies to improve the citizens' quality of life. A key novelty of the SciRoc project is the introduction of robots in smart cities and, in particular, the **European Robotics League (ERL) Smart Cities**, whose aim is to promote and show how robots will be part of the cities of the future, acting both as mobile sensors and city actuators. This adds a new challenge to ERL, which will be pursued through the organisation of two major events (in years 2019 and 2021), and supported by the synergy with the other ERL challenges carried out within the SciRoc project.

1.1 Purpose of the present document

The document reports all activities performed by the WP5 (Smart Cities competitions) during months M01-M06 (February to July 2018). We describe the initial design and the specification of the 1st ERL **Smart Cities RObotics Challenge** (the **SciRoc challenge**) to be held in the city of **Milton Keynes** from **Sept 16th to Sept 22nd, 2019**.

We provide a detailed view of the competition - venue description, tasks to achieve and clarifying examples. This document is thus meant to be read as a preliminary specification for all teams interested in attending and taking part in the event¹. Indeed, a substantial part of the presented document will be used to raise an *Expression of Interests* from potential teams (during months M08-M09, i.e. September-October 2018), following which the most popular competition tasks will be identified and selected (M09, i.e. October 2018), and the registrations for participation officially opened (M11-M14, i.e. December 2018 to March 2019). The specific competition rulebook is planned to be published after the decision of the final format of the competition (M12, i.e. January 2019).

1.2 Overview of the present document

Besides Section 1 consisting in short introduction, the deliverable consists in 3 main parts: an introduction on smart cities, the conceptualisation and design of the competition, and the description of the competition in detail. More specifically:

- **Section 2** characterises the concept of *smart city* with the main key aspects, also introducing the city of Milton Keynes as one of the most prominent examples, and then shows how smart cities relate to research in robotics, as well as to the other ERL challenges.

¹ Note that, given the different framework (w.r.t. the previous ERL challenges) that was employed for the design of the SciRoc challenge, the document is **not meant to be read as a rulebook**, i.e. no in-depth information on awards, test beds, expected inputs and outputs is provided, nor technical/specific knowledge is required to read it.

- **Section 3** introduces the SciRoc challenge in details. It includes the initial conceptualisation, how it was designed over SciRoc's first semester, and which relationships hold between the competition both with the existing ERL challenges and the Eurobench project for the development of benchmarks for humanoid robots.
- Finally, **Section 4** describes all scenarios that were designed for the competition (we call these *episodes*), including in-depth descriptions for each of them, which types of platform are allowed to participate, the locations of each episode and their specific logistics, the lists of actions to be performed at high-level, the robot functionalities that are tested, and an overview of the performance evaluation planned for the task.

2. From smart cities to ERL Smart Cities

This section presents characteristics and key aspects of smart cities, followed by the practical case of the city of Milton Keynes, which has been involved in a technology innovation program over the past years. Based on these scenarios, the last part of the section presents the idea that robots can be integrated in such complex environments, and our rationale to establish a new challenge focused on the smart cities.

2.1 Smart cities

Modern cities have become a key element of the strategies for future investments not only for the important role they play in the socio-economic growth worldwide, but also for the increasing difficulty in being environmentally sustainable [12]. As a consequence, a considerable number of efforts have been put by academic and industrial research to exploit techniques from a wide range of areas (e.g. ubiquitous computing, data management, knowledge engineering) to improve the cities' efficiency, productivity and competitiveness [2, 6, 7]. With this motivation, a new urban innovation paradigm has emerged in the last years, more often referred to as *smart cities* [5].

While smart cities have been defined along a number of dimensions [1], a set of common components can be identified in the smart city initiatives, namely:

- the **land**, i.e. the geographical urban environment involving all activities;
- the **technologies**, i.e. a networked infrastructure, that is employed to realise high quality structures, services and governance processes, improving the political efficiency and socio-economical-cultural development;
- the **citizens** (and businesses), which are involved in all activities to foster transparency and urban development; and
- the **government**, consisting of the public powers governing the city, that are appointed by the citizens for choice and decisions about the public space.

Moreover, the *smartness* of a city is generally assessed according to the following indicators:

- **smart economy**, including all activities promoting innovation, entrepreneurship, economic growth and productivity to enhance competitiveness;
- **smart people**: all activities promoting the citizens' education, plurality, flexibility, creativity, cosmopolitanism, and participation in public life to enhance the social and human capital;
- **smart governance**, all activities enhancing the citizens' participation, public and social services and transparent governance;
- **smart mobility**, i.e. the activities held to improve the management system for urban traffic, local and international accessibility, and safety to enhance the transports infrastructure;
- **smart environment**, i.e. the activities improving energy efficiency, sustainable resource management and environmental protection to protect natural resources;
- **smart living**, consisting in the activities to enhance the citizens' quality of life through cultural facilities, health conditions, individual safety, housing quality.

SciRoc promotes the vision that a smart city consists in an ecosystem of systems, where **the variety of technologies** used, **the scenarios** in which they can be applied and **the diversity and the distribution of data sources** employed is the main novelty with respect to other areas (e.g. business, education and governance) [4]. In this vision, digital hubs collect and integrate real time data about the city operations in order to support intelligent decision making and resource optimisation. Relevant scenarios include, for example, smart traffic control systems that can adapt automatically to traffic conditions, a public transport provision that adapts dynamically depending on current and predicted demand, smart grids that are able to adapt to and predict demand surges, etc. These scenarios, now being realised in a number of cities, have been implemented and prototyped in the city of Milton Keynes -- as presented in the following. Our aim is to address robots as smart city elements; to this end, we focus on *smart shopping*, where robots can support customers in a number of ways (interacting with users, supporting their shopping, handling emergency situations, etc.) and can interact with the citizens to become part of such ecosystem.

2.2 The case of Milton Keynes as a smart city

Milton Keynes is a city in Buckinghamshire, England, growing in attention not only for being an example of modern urban design, but also for being the fastest growing city in the UK (in terms of jobs, people and houses). The city engaged in the last years in a large "Future City" programme, at the centre of which was the 2014-2017 MK:Smart² project, led by the Open University (partner OU) and also including the MK City Council as a core partner.

² <http://www.mksmart.org/>

The project has created a state-of-the-art data acquisition and management infrastructure (the MK:DataHub³, or DH in short) and an Internet-of-Things network with live sensors capturing many aspects of the functionalities of the city (energy and water consumption, transport data, satellite-acquired data, social and economic datasets, and crowdsourced data from social media or specialised applications). The core idea behind the DH was that a common facility to efficiently manage, integrate and redeliver data from a variety of sources could be exploited by applications and services, reducing their development costs and enabling intelligent data management (mining, analytics, aggregation, alignment, linking) at the scale of the entire city. As a result, the DH was employed to support a large number of applications, including the MK:Insight portal⁴, which now facilitates the discovery and analysis of a variety of data collected by various departments of the MK Council, and several web/mobile app for parking monitoring and traffic forecasting to support citizen mobility, intelligent garbage collection using smart bins, and crowd monitoring using wifi sniffing⁵.

2.3 Robots in smart cities

In parallel with the recent technological developments, robotics has also matured over the last decades. This is particularly demonstrated by the large amount of efficient open source hardware and software components, the availability of reliable techniques for basic perception, manipulation and navigation tasks, as well as the increasing number of cost-accessible robotic platforms on the market [8]. Thanks to these advancements, robots and autonomous systems have been identified as one of the most important modern disruptive technologies, i.e. technologies enabling massive economic transformations in the near future [11], and policy makers worldwide are nowadays investing to support the development of urban infrastructures able to integrate robotic technologies, therefore allowing such transformations [13].

As a result, robots are being integrated more and more in modern city ecosystems, as demonstrated by autonomous cars deployed to enhance urban mobility, drones for managing first-aid emergencies, and humanoid robots for supporting elderly citizens living alone [3, 10]. Initiatives to support Research&Development for transforming cities to include robots are increasing in scale and diversity in the UK (cfr. Figure 1 below), as well as in major European cities (see projects such as URUS⁶, EUROPA⁷ and Robot-ERA⁸).

³ <http://datahub.mksmart.org/>

⁴ <http://mkinsight.org>

⁵ <http://www.mksmart.org/wp-content/uploads/2017/07/MKSmart-brochureFINAL.pdf>

⁶ <https://www.iri.upc.edu/project/show/59>.

⁷ <https://europa.informatik.uni-freiburg.de/>.

⁸ <http://www.robot-era.eu/robotera/>.

(a) Starship robots delivering food in the MK centre.

(b) Drone services for the Flying High Challenge.

Figure 1. Civic and commercial uses of robots in UK cities.

Despite the recent advances in both robotics and information technology, the integration of autonomous systems in smart cities is still at an early stage, mostly due to the difficulties of dealing with complex and large scale scenarios. Recent developments, such as autonomous cars and service robots, provide however evidence that smart cities are indeed a privileged environment for the introduction of robotic technologies.

The SciRoc challenge aims at addressing the existing gap, by specifically addressing how robots can integrate and co-operate with a complex city environment, and through assessing how robots can act both as data collectors and data consumers of the cities' digital hubs. In addition, ERL Smart Cities will host the first robotics challenges, where robots will interact with ordinary people (i.e. customers of the shopping mall), thus promoting the smart cities as a new ground for robotics competitions, offering unique opportunities to boost the robots' social acceptance (as companions or helpers) and the smart interaction with other devices and resources. European robotics researchers and developers will be called to demonstrate their technologies and systems in high profile competitive demonstrations in a smart city environment through two major *SciRoc challenges*, the first of which will be held in Milton Keynes in 2019, while the second to be held in 2021 in a city identified through a call for hosts during 2019.

2.4 Relation with the other ERLs

The SciRoc challenge builds on previous experience on competitions (RoCKIn⁹, euRathlon¹⁰, RockEU2¹¹) and keeps a strong connection with the other ERL challenges in SciRoc, that are inherited from RockEU2. In particular, the scenarios that we are devising for ERL Smart Cities have their roots in the technical abilities that are developed through the ERL-Consumer, ERL-Professional and ERL-Emergency. Due to the timing of the project, these challenges have started their activity by adopting to a large extent the pre-existing frameworks. The design of

⁹ <http://rockinrobotchallenge.eu/>.

¹⁰ <https://www.eurathlon.eu/>.

¹¹ <https://www.eu-robotics.net/eurobotics/about/projects/rockeu2.html>.

the SciRoc challenge presented below benefitted from contributions by each of the other ERL challenges. Note that the challenges of these leagues will be upgraded (i.e. with additions/refinements) at a later stage in the project, in order to create a large synergy with SciRoc in terms of robot platforms, functionalities and tasks. Details are given in the next section.

2.5 Relation with the Eurobench project

The connection between competitions and benchmarking in robotics was first explored during RoCKIn [9] and euRathlon. Competitions are typically driven by long term challenges, that can stimulate novel developments by the participating teams and, at the same time, appeal to the the general public. They also allow for an evaluation of the performances of robotic systems, with the aim of assessing the accomplishment of complex tasks. The evaluation of robotic systems, however, requires to address a number of aspects - e.g. more fine-grained definitions of the capabilities to be measured, statistical significance of the results, standardised settings etc. During RoCKIn and euRathlon, an effort was made to introduce benchmarking aspects in the competitions in order to achieve a better evaluation of the robotic systems. ERL Smart Cities inherits this approach, although it was not specifically designed with the aim of developing the benchmarking component; in fact, this is already pursued not only in the other ERL challenges, but also in European projects such as Eurobench¹², whose goal is to provide set-up and methodologies for benchmarking the performance of Humanoid Robots and Wearable Robots.

The SciRoc project has looked for possible synergies with Eurobench, with the aim of leveraging the abilities benchmarked during Eurobench to achieve complex behaviours in real, complex scenarios such as the smart cities. The result of such SciRoc-Eurobench interaction is reflected in the design of the 1st SciRoc challenge, to the extent that some of the scenarios have been refined to be addressed also by humanoid robots (see details in the next sections).

3. The 1st ERL Smart Cities Robotics Challenge

As previously mentioned, the first Smart Cities Robotics Challenge (the SciRoc challenge) will be held in Milton Keynes from **September 16th to September 22nd, 2019**. A promotional video, already available for viewing online¹³, will be used to advertise the competition throughout M08-M20 (from September 2018 to September 2019).

The competition is designed to cover the aspect of citizens' smart living, and more specifically, the smart shopping. The main novelty of the competition being that robots will have to cooperate, to a maximum extent, with the smart city digital infrastructure in order to accomplish

¹² <http://eurobench2020.eu/>.

¹³ https://www.youtube.com/channel/UC4A4EtwyzS35tHIGPnt3GWQ/featured?view_as=subscriber

their tasks. The remainder of the section describes the scenario, the environment and the digital infrastructure designed for the event.

3.1 Scenario

The competition is set in a smart shopping mall, where intelligent agents carry tasks varying from customer assistance to mall management. The *smartness* of the mall is given by the networked devices, providing static and dynamic information from a number of heterogeneous data sources, e.g. location of shops, current availability of goods and items, audio and visual inputs from CCTV cameras, crowd density sensor information, and many others. This information can be seamlessly exploited by the robots for all their tasks, as for instance:

- based on the location of the shops and the item availabilities, wheeled, human-friendly robots can welcome customers at the entrance, showing them points of interests, walking with them to the shops they are looking for. Crowd density information can be used for finding the most suitable paths in the mall at specific times;
- aerial drones perform emergency tasks, such as locating a lost dog in the shopping mall, with the help of the CCTV system for a quicker localisation;
- wheeled robots equipped with arms and effectors achieve manipulation tasks, such as delivering pre-ordered items, pushing smart trolleys, placing items in the customers' baskets or work at the checkout counters;
- service robots achieve maintenance and security tasks, such as patrolling areas for unattended or lost items, reacting to unexpected events such as drinks poured on the floor, promptly notifying the mall's management and security.

3.2 Episodes

The competition will be divided into several **episodes**. This represents an innovation of the structure of the competition, based on Functional Benchmarks¹⁴ (FBMs) and Tasks Benchmarks¹⁵ (TBMs), foreseen in the DOW and also inherited from RoCKIn [9]. Episodes are intended to be an intermediate challenge between the local tournaments' FBMs and the TBMs. Even though the methodology and the approach to the competition are de facto unchanged, the proposed format based on episodes is designed to make a step forward

¹⁴ Functionality Benchmarks evaluate the performance of robot subsystems dedicated to specific functionalities, defining a precise setup in which a single robot functionality can be evaluated [9]. Examples of FBMs include visual/auditory/sensorial perception, (basic) navigation, or speech understanding.

¹⁵ Task Benchmarks evaluate the performance of robot systems facing simple or complex tasks that require the integration and interaction of different functionalities, i.e. a set of interacting robot subsystems (navigation, perception, and manipulation) are examined together at the same time. Examples of TBMs can be "placing a plate on the table", "setting the table for a tea party of three", "cleaning the table after the tea party", all or which requiring multiple functionalities, such as speech understanding, perception, navigation, and object manipulation.

towards their application in a realistic scenario, to allow for a better communication towards the general public and to lower the entry level for the competing teams.

3.2.1 Characterisation of episodes

An episode places a given functionality, tested during a specific FBM in one of the other ERL challenges, into a more social and operational context. This means that, during an episode, the tested behaviour requires an extension and/or specialization of the basic ERL functionalities and the integration with other system components, but limits the efforts for their development (using, for instance, off-the-shelf solutions). Although the goal is to target specifically one functionality (or exceptionally, two), an effort for integrating the main functionality and the other ones might be required in order to complete the episode.

For example, given the *Navigation* FBM in the ERL-Customer, an episode can be *Navigation in a crowded environment*, which stresses the functionality of navigating, and adds the challenge of a dynamic environment, for which other functionalities (e.g. people detection and tracking) are required to improve the behaviour of the robot planner.

The design of the episodes allows us to build a more articulate narrative for the competition, thus making robotic functionalities more appealing to a non-expert audience. Moreover, episodes are designed to also give the possibility to teams from different ERL challenges to compete in the same episode.

3.2.2 Categories of episodes

Episodes are organised into categories depending on the task to achieve and the type of robots involved. We group them into three categories:

- **HRI&Mobility:** all episodes involving robots able to show social behaviours, such as verbally interacting with (human) customers or navigating respecting proxemics, in line with the current ERL-Consumer. These are meant for any robot (wheeled, or legged) with navigational and verbal communication.
- **Manipulation:** this category includes all episodes requiring robots to achieve manipulation tasks, applying ERL-Professional services to the smart city context. Episodes here are meant for any robot able to navigate and equipped with arms and effectors for the manipulation of objects.
- **Emergency:** the last category comprehends tasks and challenges addressed by small VTOL aerial robots, along the lines of the ERL-Emergency. Any VTOL aerial platform able to carry and deliver items in specific locations, navigate in outdoor and indoor spaces, detect and avoid obstacles can take part to episodes of this category.

Please note that the above categories resemble those of the ERLs, however some of the functionalities are shared among them. In addition, note that some episodes have been

specifically designed to allow some of the challenges to be addressed by humanoids robots, as part of the collaboration that SciRoc holds with the Eurobench project.

3.2.3 Episode selection process

In order to maximise the team interests and attendance, the SciRoc challenge is defined a specific competition design process, articulated in four steps:

1. **Episode definition:** first, a number of episodes relevant to the competition are designed by the consortium, distributed across the three categories presented in Section 3.2. At present, a set of 12 episodes have been defined.
2. **Episode advertisement:** in a second step, all episodes are advertised as part of SciRoc's dissemination activities. While advertising the event, we will gather episode preferences through the call for intention to participate directly from the teams expressing interest.
3. **Final selection:** once gathered interests over a time span (e.g. two months), the episodes that have raised more preferences will be selected as the official competition episodes.
4. **Rulebook publication:** the rulebook of the competition for the final selection will be subsequently released.

3.3 Competition environment

The competition will be organised in the Centre:MK shopping mall¹⁶, whose floorplan is shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Floorplan of the the Centre:MK shopping mall.

The area is articulated in two main allées (or corridors), along which several shops are located, and a large exhibition area, called *Middleton Hall*, surrounded by cafés and a large retailer (Figure 3).

¹⁶ <https://www.thecentremk.com/>

Figure 3. (a) Middleton Hall area (empty) and (b) the adjacent allées.

A competition *Arena* will be set up in Middleton Hall using a fencing system. The arena will be divided in two sub-areas, one area comprehending all necessary equipment for team set-up (tables, chairs, screens, power and ethernet cables), and one area where each of the specific competition episodes will be held. The corridors adjacent to Middleton Hall will also be employed, for episodes where a specific interaction with the customers is foreseen. A specific netting will be employed for episodes involving drones.

3.4 Data infrastructure for the competition

The MK:DataHub is an aggregator of information from a variety of heterogeneous data sources in MK, thematically organised in datasets. These are accessible through well-defined APIs, documented in the developer section of the MK:DataHub web portal¹⁷. Once registered, developers can push and get data freely.

Information in datasets is structured (JSON format mostly, other format sometimes available), and can be both dynamic (e.g. streams of sensor data describing parking lot occupancy) or static (such as businesses of the city, post-processed images from CCTV camera readings). Examples of datasets are (not all to be used within ERL Smart Cities):

- **traffic and mobility** data: e.g. live bus routes, their locations and passenger count, live road traffic busyness, live sensor data from car parks, and live frequency of parking ticket issued;
- **geographic** data: e.g. satellite and aerial imageries, location of parking bays and spaces, bus stops locations;
- **business** data: e.g. food retailers metadata (name, website, address, description of available goods), hospitals and doctor surgeries (location and static information);
- **demographics**: disability living allowance, census data provided by the council;

¹⁷ <https://datahub.mksmart.org/developer/>

- **environmental** data: live temperature, humidity, air pressure from weather stations, weather forecast, crowdsourced street maintenance status, recycling bins meters readings, live water level of the canals;
- **social media** data: aggregated data from Twitter feeds (e.g. #mk, #mkpolice, etc...).

The MK:DataHub is a resource under constant development, as new data and datasets can and are regularly updated/added.

The SciRoc challenge will aim at demonstrating that robots can be both **data consumers and data producers of a smart city infrastructure**. This means that robots can be used as mobile sensors to produce information for the MK:DataHub (e.g. drones that monitor the parking lots or the roads' congestion), and that the information they produce can further be used by other robots to accomplish their own tasks. For this reason, each of the episodes is designed to have a certain degree of interaction with the MK:DataHub. A more technical specification of how such interaction will take place will be presented along each episode in Section 4.

3.5 Tentative schedule

While the challenge will be held in September 2019, ERL Smart Cities has planned the selection process according to the following tentative timeline:

- (Sep 1st, 2018) *Call for Expression of Interests*; we intend here to gather interests around the competition and identify potential teams and the most appealing competition episodes (closing date, October 10th).
- (October 15th, 2018) Publication of the first *Call for Participation*, after episode selection.
- (December 1st, 2018) Opening of team submissions (closing date January 31st, 2019).
- (January 1st, 2019) Publication of the first draft of the *Challenge Rulebook*: the specific rulebook will be published for the participating teams.
- (February 15th, 2019) Notification of accepted teams.
- (March 1st, 2019) Second *Call for Participation* (closing date March 31st).
- (April 15th, 2019): Notification of accepted teams.

Advertisement of the SciRoc challenge will be done in several venues and at different stages of the process. In particular, a dedicated booth at the IEEE/RSJ International Conference on Intelligent Robots and Systems (IROS2018), to attract team interests and episode preferences is already planned (Oct 1st-5th, 2018).

Additionally, a tentative timeline for the week of the competition is below:

Monday 16/09/19	Tuesday 17/09/19	Wednesday 18/09/19	Thursday 19/09/19	Friday 20/09/19	Saturday 21/09/19	Sunday 22/09/19
Team set up	Team set up	Competition D1	Competition D2	Competition D3	Grand Finale	Dismantle
	Inaugural event		Gala dinner		Awards	

4. Specification of the competition

The final part of this document includes a more specific description of the competition episodes, as follows:

- Category **HRI&Mobility**:
 1. (E01) Attract a customer
 2. (E02) Shopping guide
 3. (E03) Delivering coffee shop orders
 4. (E04) Take the elevator
 5. (E05) Unattended item
 6. (E06) Wiping a drink poured on the floor
- Category **Manipulation**:
 7. (E07) Serving goodies
 8. (E08) At the check-out desk
 9. (E09) Cart push
 10. (E10) Open the door
- Category **Emergency**:
 11. (E11) Finding a lost dog with a drone
 12. (E12) Fast delivery of emergency pills

Note that the uneven distribution of the episodes among the categories has been chosen to reflect the potential distribution of participating teams, based on the consortium past experiences.

Besides a general description, we present for each episode:

- **Platforms allowed**, i.e. the list of all platforms allowed for the episodes;
- **Setting**, i.e. the location and logistics for the episode;
- **Procedure**, i.e. the list of actions to be performed;
- **DH interaction**, i.e. the datasets, data, and formats required to achieve the task, which type of interaction it consists of (robot as data consumers or data producers);

- **Main functionality(ies)**, i.e. the main functionality(ies) that is the technical focus of the episode;
- **Auxiliary functionalities**, i.e. the other required functionalities that are required, to be implemented also with off-the-shelf solutions;
- **Achievements**, i.e. an overview of the robot achievements for the evaluation
- **Penalising behaviours**, i.e. the criteria for the penalisation of a robot.

Inspired by the ERL evaluation methodology, scoring will be calculated by considering both achievements and penalising behaviors. More specifically, a team's final score for a given episode will be evaluated as the sum of the achievements. If two or more teams reach the same number of achievements, the penalising behaviors will be also considered.

4.1 Episode 01 - Attract a customer

General description. The episode is focused on customer assistance in the context of the SciRoc challenge. The robot approaches a customer (or a group of customers) and provides information about the competition with the aim of convincing the customers to visit one of the episodes. The robot is expected to interact with regular customers of the shopping mall. Moreover, the robot should be able to handle the interaction with multiple customers. When the customer has decided which episode he/she wants to see, the robot must provide a description of the path to get to the proper location. Optionally, the robot should then accompany the customers to the first landmark in the path.

Platforms allowed. Any robot capable of Navigation, Perception, and Human-Robot Interaction capabilities can be used in this episode.

Setting. The episode takes place in one of the two allées of the mall, in the vicinity of one of the entrances. The episode starts with the robot placed near the entrance. Later the robot takes customers to the shopping mall area where the episodes are taking place.

Procedure. At the start, the robot must identify a group of customers and gather their attention. The robot should then approach the customers and starts a dialog aiming at explaining the episodes of the smart city competition. The dialog ends when one of the customers indicates an episode to visit or declares no interest in the competition. In the first case, the robot provides the directions, guides the customer to the selected episode area and greets him/her. In the latter case, the robot simply greets the customers.

Customers will be chosen from the visitors of the competition. They will be asked to fill-in a questionnaire upon termination of the episode. The episode is repeated so that a number of successful interactions is reached (5) or a maximum number of attempts to approach a group of people is reached.

DH interaction. *Type: data consumption.* The MK:DataHub will provide static resources such as the map of the mall/arena and information (metadata) about episode locations. Dynamic information will be provided as well, for example whether an episode is taking place or not. The robot will be able to access this information through dedicated APIs.

Main functionality(ies). The main functionalities tested are HRI using speech, gesture and facial expressions.

Auxiliary functionalities. Other required functionalities are People Recognition, Navigation & person guidance.

Achievements.

- Gathering the attention of a group of customers.
- Suitably approach the group, using human- and social-aware navigation norms.
- Successfully engage on a dialog with the customers on the competition.
- One customer chooses the episode.
- A path is planned to the episode area, and successfully traversed.

Penalising behaviours.

- Touching any customer.
- Misunderstanding customer requests.
- Obstructing the way of the customers.
- Bumping into shopping mall walls and/or furniture.

4.2 Episode 02 - Shopping Guide

General description. A customer has gone to the mall for some shopping. Robotic shopping assistants operate in the mall to help customers during their shopping. One of their roles is to accompany customers while wandering in the mall, properly reacting to unexpected situations. The robot task is therefore to *safely follow a person through a public space*: the robot will have to conduct proper behaviour according to the events, e.g., receiving instructions from the customer (“please wait for me for a moment”); dealing with obstacles and/or people standing in the way; following the customer through narrow passages; or detecting objects accidentally lost by the customer.

Platforms allowed. Any robot capable of Navigation, Perception, and Human-Robot Interaction capability can be used in this episode.

Setting. The episode takes place inside the shopping mall, both in the main wide corridors and inside a shop. A specific area inside which the robot will have to follow the customer should be specified. It should comprehend:

- a wider part, maybe with a higher presence of people;
- at least a narrow passage, simulating the entrance of a shop;
- a narrower corridor, like the lane of a shop, where people can be encountered, as well as other objects to be avoided (trolleys, items fallen from the shelves, and so on).

Procedure. At the beginning of the episode, the robot may be required to memorise the customer that it will have to follow (as s/he can be not specified from the beginning). The customer may use some basic vocal interaction to tell the robot to behave in a certain way, e.g., asking to wait outside a shop.

DH interaction. *Type: data consumption and generation.* The MK:DataHub will provide location of the shops in the mall, as well as availability of products. Additionally, the MK:DataHub may provide crowd monitoring information. The robot should produce data about the crowdedness of some areas, detect potential hazards found on the way (slippery liquid poured on the floor) and inform about displaced items in the shop lanes.

Main functionality(ies). The main functionalities tested are Person tracking and following, Social Navigation in dynamic environments, Crowd detection and analysis and Semantic mapping.

Auxiliary functionalities. Other functionalities required are Spoken Language Understanding and Object Recognition.

Achievements.

- Follow the customer inside a narrow passage
- Navigate around group of people
- Follow operator behind the group of persons
- Understanding and reacting to the customer “wait” command (stop and restart when required)
- Correctly reporting about crowdedness to the MK:Datahub.

Penalizing behaviors.

- Touching the customer.
- Misunderstanding or ignoring customer requests.
- Obstructing the way of the customer.
- Bumping into shopping mall walls and/or furniture.

- Stopping following the customer.
- Following another person.
- Not producing the information required for the MK:Datahub.

4.3 Episode 03 - Delivering coffee shop orders

General Description. In this episode the robot will assist people in a coffee shop to take care of customers, by taking orders and bringing objects to and from customers' tables.

The main functionality that is evaluated in this episode is people perception. Additional side functionalities are navigation, speech synthesis and recognition.

Platforms allowed. A mobile robot equipped with a tray, a planar surface or any way of transporting small items (e.g., a cup of coffee - possibly empty). Sensors for people perception and navigation in the environment are also needed.

Setting. a coffee shop, with a few tables and typical objects (e.g, coffee cups, napkins, ...). A set of people sitting at the table, some tables are clean, some will have objects on it.

Procedure. The robot is placed in a starting location in front of the tables. Some customers will try to get attention of the robot (e.g., by calling and waving at it). The robot will reach the table and will assess the status of the table (either clean or with objects). If the table is clean, the robot will accept an order from the customers and will report the order to the kitchen. It will remember the order and will deliver the objects to that table. If the table is full, the robot will ask the customers if they want to place some objects on its tray to bring them back to the kitchen. If the robot detects that people are giving attention to it, it will tell the customers about special events occurring in MK in the following days.

Notes: 1) no manipulation actions are required, the objects are placed and gathered by people to and from the tray on the robot, 2) objects to deliver are such that they will fit on the robot space.

DH interaction. *Type: data consumption.* Orders are placed through an application which is connected to the MK:DataHub. The MK:DataHub keeps track of all the orders. Additionally, the robot can gather information from the MK:DataHub about next events to refer them to customers.

Main functionality(ies). The main functionality tested is Person and Object Perception.

Auxiliary functionalities. In addition, other functionalities that are needed are Navigation, Speech synthesis and Spoken Language Understanding to interact with customers.

Achievements.

- Correctly identifying people calling for the robot.
- Reaching the table.
- Evaluating the status of the table and performing the correct action.
- Taking and deliver the order.
- Taking items to the kitchen.
- Understanding people giving attention to the robot.
- Tell about events in MK.

Penalising behaviours.

- Hitting or damaging the table.
- Wrongly evaluating the status of the table.
- Pouring or crashing any of the carried items.
- Misinterpreting customer requests.

4.4 Episode 04 - Take the elevator

General description. The robot must take the elevator crowded with customers to reach a service located in another floor. The robot should interact with the MK:DataHub to discover which floor it must reach to accomplish its task. The robot must be able to take the elevator together with regular customers of the shopping mall. The robot should be able to enter and exit the elevator at the right floor in the presence of people nearby and/or inside. To perform the episode the robot can interact with the customers in spoken language. The robot is not supposed to push buttons (although it could in a more complex version of the task), and it can ask the people around to do it.

Platforms allowed. Any robot that can navigate and interact with people in spoken language.

Setting. The episode takes place in the shopping mall, at one of the elevators. The customers are chosen from the visitors of the competition after a clearance check, where they accept to take the elevator with the robot, and to fill-in a questionnaire upon termination of the episode. The number of customers can be defined in order to provide an environment of increasing difficulty.

Procedure. The episode starts with the robot placed near the elevator. When the service is requested to the robot, the robot must find out which floor it has to reach. The robot should move in the area nearby the elevator where people are standing to take the elevator. The robot announces its intention of taking the elevator and then interacts with the customers to enter and exit at the right floor. The duration of the overall task is 5 minutes.

DH interaction. *Type: data consumption.* The MK:DataHub will provide the location of shops in terms of the floor where they are located. In addition, the MK:DataHub could provide information about the status of the elevator: which floor it is at, or whether the doors are open or closed.

Main functionality(ies). The main functionality tested is Navigation respecting proxemics.

Auxiliary functionalities. Other required functionalities are Spoken Dialogue (beyond command interpretation) and People Detection.

Achievements.

- Entering the elevator.
- Recognising the floor to be reached.
- Getting out from the elevator at the right floor.

Penalising behaviours.

- Touching the customers.
- Misunderstanding their requests.
- Obstructing the way to the customers.

4.5 Episode 05 - Unattended item

General description. The episode is focused on the task of detecting unattended items. The robot is assigned an area of the shopping mall to patrol looking for unattended items (i.e. bags, packages), that are left in an location, where there are no customers taking care of them. The robot must ensure that the package is unattended, possibly interacting with customers that are in the vicinity of the item. Moreover, the robot must communicate to the MK:DataHub to check whether the detected item matches any of the descriptions of the items declared lost to the lost&found service. When the item is actually believed to be unattended, the robot must communicate to the MK:DataHub that an unattended item has been found, its location and whether it can possibly be one of the items reported to the lost&found service.

Platforms allowed. Any robot that can move, detect and classify objects and interact with people in spoken language.

Setting. The episode takes place in the shopping mall, in a dedicated area to be patrolled. The episode starts with the robot placed at any location within the area. Two items are placed in arbitrary locations, where there are customers standing nearby. The customers are chosen from the visitors of the competition. They will be asked to stand near the item talking.

Procedure. The robot should start exploring the area searching for the unattended item. If the robot detects an item should then interact with the MK:DataHub to determine whether the item belongs to the lost&found. The MK:DataHub will provide a description of the item, category, plus some characteristic features. Based on the observation of the scene, on the information provided by the lost&found, and, possibly, on a dialog with a customer, the robot must determine whether the item is or not unattended. The robot must communicate to the MK:DataHub the category and location of the unattended item and whether it matches the description of one or more of the lost items reported to the lost&found service.

DH interaction. *Type: data consumption and generation.* The MK:DataHub has to communicate the area to patrol to the robot. Moreover, the list of lost&found objects should be provided, in terms of visual description (e.g. pictures or images). The robot has to update the status of lost&found object in the MK:DataHub after the patrol is terminated.

Main functionality(ies). The main functionality tested is Object Recognition (matching a description) and People Behavior Understanding.

Auxiliary functionalities. Other required functionalities are Navigation, Object Detection, Spoken Language Interaction.

Achievements.

- Correct detection of an object.
- Correct attribution to the category “unattended”.
- Correct communication to the MK:DataHub.

Penalising behaviours.

- Touching any customer.
- Obstructing the way of the customers.
- Misunderstanding user responses.
- Misclassifying an object as “unattended”.
- Failing in updating the status of the objects in the MK:DataHub.

4.6 Episode 06 - Wiping a drink poured on the floor

General description. The episode is focused on the task of cleaning an area where a customer reported an accidental fall of a cup filled with a drink that is poured on the floor. The robot is informed by the MK:DataHub that a customer reported that a drink is accidentally poured on the floor and the floor must be wiped to avoid slippage and further spreading of the dirt. The robot, equipped with a wiper, should reach the specified location and clean it. While

cleaning the robot must ensure that no customer is stepping on the dirt area. When finished, the robot must communicate to the MK:DataHub the location of the dirty area.

Platforms allowed. Any robot that can navigate and localize in the environment, spot the presence of a liquid on the floor and wipe the floor (by covering the dirty surface with the cleaning device).

Setting. The episode takes place in the shopping mall, within a set of predefined areas. The episode starts with the robot placed at any location within shopping mall, when a communication of the need to clean a nearby location is issued by the MK:DataHub.

Procedure. The robot is supposed to know the map of the area from the MK:DataHub. The robot should move to the designated location and spot the dirty area. In order to wipe the floor the robot will be equipped with a simple device (e.g. a sponge or a wiping towel) that will be mounted on a rigid frame easily attachable to the robot so that it will touch the floor without creating a significant friction. The wiper will be the same for all the teams. The cleaning will consist in covering the dirt area with the wiper. During the cleaning customers can pass by and the robot must ensure that they do not step on the dirt. Finally the robot must communicate to the MK:DataHub that the designated area has been cleaned.

DH interaction. *Type: data consumption and generation.* The MK:DataHub communicates the broad area where a liquid has been poured. After cleaning, the robot has to update status of the area in the MK:DataHub.

Main functionality(ies). The main functionalities tested are Detection of liquid on the floor and Coverage strategies.

Auxiliary functionalities. Other required functionalities are People detection (direction), Navigation, Spoken Language Interaction.

Achievements.

- Detection and localization of the dirty area.
- Successful cleaning of the liquid.
- Successful interaction with passing by customers.
- Report to the MK:DataHub.

Penalising behaviours.

- Touching the customers.
- Further spreading of the dirt (by stepping on the drink or by letting a customer step on the drink).

- Failing in reporting to the MK:DataHub.

4.7 Episode 07 - Serving goodies

General description. The robot is in one the booths of the mall. On the shelf of the booth are the goodies displayed for sale to the customers. The customers can place orders through a tablet. The robot must move behind the display and collect the requested packages for the customer place them in a box and place the box on a tray where the customer can pick it. The choice of the setting will be refined based on the possibility of finding a sponsor interested in advertising its products (i.e. Lindt, Haribo, Cadbury...).

Platforms allowed. Any mobile platform with a manipulator.

Setting. one of the booths available in the central area of the venue.

Procedure. The episode has a fixed duration. It starts when the robot has been (manually) positioned behind the shelf with a display. The customer who is randomly chosen among the mall visitors places the order via the chosen interaction modality. The total number of goodies is fixed, but not their type. The robot can then collect the items, place them in the box and deliver the box to the customer.

DH interaction. *Type: data consumption and generation.* The order is placed via an application connected to the MK:DataHub. It will communicate to the robot what to pick (and in which quantity) from the different goodies. Moreover, after having finalised the order, the robot has to update the quantity of each product in the MK:DataHub.

Main functionality(ies). The main functionality tested is Object Perception and Manipulation (the latter including both planning and execution).

Auxiliary functionalities. None.

Achievements.

- Correct composition of the order.
- Correct placing of the items in the box.
- Correct updating of the MK:DataHub.

Penalizing behaviors.

- Damaging an item.
- Letting an item fall on the floor.
- Damaging the basket or the checkout desk.
- Letting the basket fall to the floor.

- Wrongly updating the MK:DataHub.

4.8 Episode 08 - At the checkout desk

General description. The robot is in front of the checkout desk of a shop or supermarket. On the desk are the items purchased by a customer, which are a set of different objects differing in size and shape as well as in physical properties (such as hardness/deformability, fragility, surface properties). For instance, possible items may comprise: a metal soup can (cylindrical, heavy, not deformable, not fragile, not slippery), a paper flour packet (box-shaped, heavy, deformable, not fragile, quite slippery), a plastic blister containing two light bulbs (irregular shape, light, deformable in some places, fragile, not slippery) and a pack of sponges (box-shaped, light, highly deformable, not fragile, not slippery).

Upon the desk, beside the purchased items, is a shopping basket of the type generally used in grocery shops or supermarket for small quantities of products: i.e., made of plastic or metal, open from the top side, with holes in the sides that can be used to perceive contents. The basket is not affixed to the desk in any way, so that if pushed by the robot it will move.

A good choice for the first editions of the episode is a basket made from metal wire: heavy (thus difficult to move) and with sides that are very transparent to perception. In later editions, the episode may be made more difficult by using a plastic basket, which is lighter and more obstructive perceptually. The task of the robot is to take the items from the desk and store them in the basket, without dropping or damaging them. The space in the basket is limited; moreover, the purchased items, when in the basket, should remain within the volume of the basket without protruding from its top: therefore the robot should take into account the shape of the items in order to plan and execute an efficient storage configuration. For first editions, this requirement may be made easy to comply with by making the item set small and/or choosing small items; later, difficulty may be raised by increasing the number and/or size of the items, as well as by including items which are difficult to manipulate.

Platforms allowed. Any mobile platform with a manipulator.

Setting. The actual checkout desk of one of the shops of the shopping mall, possibly moved out of its usual position to help visibility by the public. No human-robot interaction occurs during the episode.

Procedure. The episode has a fixed duration. It starts when the robot has been (manually) positioned in front of the checkout desk and it ends when a timeout is reached. During the course of the episode the robot can move the items (both those outside and those inside the basket) as many times as needed. When the timeout is reached the robot must stop and the items in the basket are evaluated by human referees.

DH interaction. *Type: data consumption and generation.* The list of goods to place in the basket is communicated by the MK:DataHub. It will communicate to the robot what to pick (and in which quantity) from the different goodies. Moreover, after having finalised the task, the robot has to update the quantity of each product in the MK:DataHub.

Main functionality(ies). The main functionalities tested are Object Perception and Manipulation (the latter including both planning and execution).

Auxiliary functionalities. Other required functionality is strategic planning to optimally store the items into the basket.

Achievements.

- Correctly placing the items into the basket.
- Not damaging any items.
- No items protrude above the top of the side walls of the basket.
- Correct updating of the MK:DataHub.

Penalising behaviours.

- Damaging an item.
- Letting an item fall to the floor.
- Damaging the basket or the checkout desk.
- Letting the basket fall to the floor.
- Wrongly updating the MK:DataHub.

4.9 Episode 09 - Cart push

General description. A customer decides to pay a visit to the shopping mall to do some shopping. S/he likes to visit shops, but hates to bring around her/his purchases. Fortunately, the mall has some new robot shopping helpers. In fact, as soon as the customer arrives at the mall, one of the “robot helpers” is assigned to her/him. The robot will take care of pushing the shopping cart, following the customer through the corridors and shops of the mall while keeping a safe distance; however, whenever the customer needs to put something in the cart or pull something out, s/he only has to ask the robot to “Come here” and the robot will park the cart next to her/him, waiting for the “Let’s go!” command before resuming movements. A final “Park the cart” command tells the robot to park the cart and stop.

Platforms allowed. Any platform possessing actuators capable of physically interacting with the cart’s handle (which is a standard bar of the type used by human shopping cart users), and of receiving vocal commands.

Setting. A small area of the shopping mall comprising part of a corridor and two shops opening on it. The environment includes a section of a wall, against which the shopping cart is parked at the start and at the end. In the area are present fixed obstacles (benches, columns, trash bins, ...).

Procedure. Before the start of the episode, a customer reaches the robot at its starting position. The episode starts, and the robot (without need for commands from the customer) collects the shopping cart that is parked in a nearby space against a wall. Then the shopping begins: the customer visits 2 different shops, one very open and one where the customer has to navigate through obstacles (dress stands). The robot must avoid losing the customer, even when a person dressed with perfectly matched colors walks between the robot and the customer. In general, other customers and obstacles of different types are present in the area. During the episode, two times the customer commands the robot to “Come here” and then gives the “Let’s go” command, each time after visiting one of the shops. When the customer and the robot are back in the shopping cart parking area, s/he tells the robot to “Park the cart”. The episode ends when the cart is back in its parking position. During the episode, the robot should never be more than 5 m from the customer. If the robot perceives that its distance from her/him is more than 3m, it can ask the customer (vocally) “Wait for me”. In this case, the customer stops and gives the robot some time to catch up with her/him (i.e. get their distance below 3m).

DH interaction. None.

Main functionality(ies). The main functionalities tested are Robot Control under external forces.

Auxiliary functionalities. Other required functionalities are Localization and Navigation, Speech Understanding and Grasping (of the cart’s handle).

Achievements.

- The robot correctly retrieves the shopping cart from its parking space.
- The robot correctly reacts to the first “Come here” command.
- The robot correctly reacts to the first “Let’s go” command.
- The robot does not lose the customer when the similarly-dressed person walks behind them.
- The robot correctly reacts to the second “Come here” command.
- The robot correctly reacts to the second “Let’s go” command.
- The robot correctly reacts to the “Park the cart” command.
- The robot correctly parks the shopping cart in its parking space.

Penalising behaviors.

- The robot lightly touches a person with its body or the shopping cart.
- The robot hits an obstacle with its body or the shopping cart.
- Acceleration (linear or rotational) of the shopping cart exceeds predefined values.
- Velocity (linear or rotational) of the shopping cart exceeds predefined values.
- The robot requires repetition of a command to execute it.
- The distance between the customer and the robot goes over 5m (applied every time this occurs, and, for each occurrence, applied again every 30s from previous application).
- The robot asks the customer to “Wait for it” (first request is not penalised, each subsequent requests is).
- The robot hits a person with its body or the shopping cart.
- The robot damages the shopping cart.
- The robot damages the shopping mall.

4.10 Episode 10 - Open the door

General description. Doors are ubiquitous in human environments. There are many types of doors, some of which are easier to operate than others for a robot.

Unfortunately, one of the most difficult types of doors is the most frequent of all, especially when considering private environments: the door swinging around hinges defining a vertical axis coincident with one side of the door, with a locking handle. To unlock the door, usually the handle needs to be rotated (around a horizontal axis perpendicular to the surface of the door) while moving, *at the same time*, the door from its closed position.

Other version of this type of swinging door are used in public spaces: these, while usually lacking the locking mechanism (and therefore the need to rotate the handle to unlock the door) are generally fitted with mechanisms for automatic closure that significantly increase the torque needed to operate the door. The resisting torque (due to the closure mechanism) frequently has a non-linear relation to the opening angle: for instance, it often provides the highest torque values at the extremes of the angular range.

A final difficulty is due to the very dimensions of doors: such dimensions are typically sufficiently large (w.r.t. typical robot arm lengths) to force a robot manipulating the door to move its base during the manipulation.

In the end, the capability of correctly operating doors with vertical-axis hinges is a necessity for any robot designed to effectively operate in human environments (and especially homes). However, this “door manipulation” functionality requires that the robot is capable of:

- Estimating the direction where the door opens (e.g., by trying each way and using force feedback to determine if resisting torque is compatible with a door opening that way);
- Correctly controlling the motion of the door in presence of variable resisting torque;
- Operating the locking handle (if present) in order to unlock the door.

Platforms allowed. Any robot platform with a movable base, an arm, and end effector capable of gripping a door handle (though different -though arguably less generally useful- configurations are applicable).

Setting. When the episode starts, the robot is in front of a wall at least 4 m long, facing such wall. In the center of the wall is a closed door. If the handle of the door is of the locking type, the door is also locked by it. The door has the typical look (frame, panels, handle) of one of the inner doors of an apartment. No other doors are present within 15 m from the robot.

Procedure. The robot must identify the door and approach it, remaining on the same side of the wall where it is at the start of the episode. When it reaches the door, the robot is required to identify the handle and use it to unlock the door (if the handle is a locking one), then open it completely. Complete opening is reached when the door orientation wrt its original orientation is within a specified tolerance from 90°.

The robot is considered as having completed the opening when two conditions occur at the same time:

1. The end effector is no more in contact with the handle;
2. The door is stationary.

The robot can only interact with the door using the handle. If the handle is a locking one, the robot must correctly operate it to unlock the door before the door can be moved.

If the door is of the bi-directional type, the opening direction of the door (away from the robot or towards the robot) is not known in advance, otherwise it is known to the robot. The only other information known to the robot at the start of the episode is that the door rotates around a vertical axis coincident with the side which is farther from the handle. In order to operate the door, the robot must autonomously ascertain:

- On what side of the door is the handle/are the hinges;
- If the door handle is a locking one (rotating) or not (fixed);
- (for bi-directional doors) What is the opening direction of the door (this can be done by trying both: only one will work).

While the door is moving, the robot must control its movement even in the presence of torque applied to the door by the door torque actuators (if present). The only predefined rules about the way this torque is related to the door opening angle are:

1. The relation does not change over time;

2. Torque is zero when the opening angle is 0° or 90° (or, possibly, within an angular range from each of these values which is unknown to the robot).

Please note that (as it happens with real doors) the relation between torque and angle may change according to the direction in which the door is rotating. Also, the torque applied to the door by its torque actuators (if present) is generally nonzero for angles (sufficiently) different from 0° and 90° : therefore the door moves on its own when not controlled by the robot, except at the extremes of its range.

DH interaction. None.

Main functionality(ies). The main functionality tested is Manipulation.

Auxiliary functionalities. Mobility/Navigation.

Achievements.

- Correctly opening the door.
- Correctly passing through the open door.
- Correctly pushing down the door handle.

Penalising behaviours.

- Damaging the door or the door handle.
- Stumbling on the door while crossing it.
- Being unable to open the door.
- Being unable to grasp the door handle.

4.11 Episode 11 - Finding a lost dog with a drone

General description. The aerial robot must perform a surveillance flight looking for a dog that a customer has reported it was lost in the mall centre. The robot must be able to fly autonomously around the area, detect the lost dog and report its location. There can be obstacles in the flying area that must be avoided during the flight. Moreover, the robot is part of a “monitoring” infrastructure that should report about the status of the mall continuously while performing other duties. Two other objects may be present on the ground, such as a garbage bag and a cardboard box. The robot should report their position if one or more of these are spot while looking for the dog. Of course, the robot should report and update continuously the position of the dog

Platforms allowed. VTOL aerial robot that can navigate in outdoor and indoor spaces, detect and avoid obstacles.

Setting. The episode must take place inside the flying arena. The lost dog can be represented by a teddy dog mounted on a small RC car, so it can be moved around the arena.

Procedure. The request to look for a lost dog reaches a surveillance centre. The aerial robot takes off and starts a mission to find the lost dog around the arena. During the flight, the robot must detect and avoid obstacles. The dog must be detected and its position estimated by the robotic system, and reported to the surveillance centre, along with live video feed. Once the dog is found, the robot can go back to the take-off location. Meanwhile looking for the dog, if any of the two other objects (i.e. plastic bag or cardboard box) is detected, its position has to be reported to the MK:DataHub.

DH interaction. *Type: data generation.* The aerial robot should update the MK:DataHub with the location of the dog continuously, as well as of the other two objects.

Main functionality(ies). The main functionality tested is Object Perception.

Auxiliary functionalities. Other required functionality is Indoor Navigation.

Achievements.

- Detecting the dog and reporting its correct location.
- Detecting the other objects and reporting their correct location.
- Transmitting live images/video to the MK:DataHub.
- Landing at the starting location.

Penalising behaviours.

- Manual interventions to the aerial robot in case it needs to be recovered from a failure.
- Hitting any of the structures in the flying arena (obstacles, safety net...).
- Damaging the structures in the flying arena (obstacles, safety net...).
- Hitting the dog.
- Leaving the flying arena.
- Failing in transmitting data to the MK:DataHub.

4.12 Episode 12 - Fast delivery of emergency pills

General description. The aerial robot must attend an emergency situation in which a first-aid kit needs to be delivered to a customer. The robot must be able to fly autonomously to the customer location as fast as possible. The robot might need to detect and avoid possible obstacles on the way, and it must take into account that GPS coverage is not always guaranteed.

Platforms allowed. VTOL aerial robot that can carry and deliver items in specific locations, navigate in outdoor and indoor spaces, detect and avoid obstacles.

Setting. The episode must take place inside the flying arena. Within the arena, a marquee can be installed to represent an indoor mall space, and the customer can be represented by a mannequin placed inside the marquee.

Procedure. A first-aid kit request reaches a medical centre with medicine storage. The responsible of such centre fills the first-aid kit ready to be delivered, and attaches it to the aerial robot which is located in the take-off position. The robot takes off with the kit towards the marquee location, detecting and avoiding different obstacles on the way. Once at the marquee, it must enter through an opening, detect the mannequin, land nearby and release the first-aid kit on the floor. Once delivered, the aerial robot must take off again, exit the marquee and reach again the initial take-off location, ready for the next delivery.

DH interaction. *Type: data consumption and generation.* The broad position of the customer in need is communicated to the aerial robot by the MK:DataHub. The robot should provide images/video to the MK:DataHub during the mission.

Main functionality(ies). The main functionalities tested are Autonomous Navigation in outdoor and indoor unstructured environments and Obstacle Detection.

Auxiliary functionalities. Other required functionality is Person Detection.

Achievements.

- Entering the marquee.
- Detecting the customer.
- Landing and delivering the first-aid kit.
- Exiting the marquee.
- Landing at the starting location.
- Transmitting live images/video to the MK:DataHub.

Penalising behaviours.

- Manual interventions to the aerial robot in case it needs to be recovered from a failure.
- Hitting any of the structures in the flying arena (marquee, obstacles, safety net...).
- Flying/landing closer than a predefined small distance to the mannequin.
- Damaging the structures in the flying arena (marquee, obstacles, safety net...).
- Hitting the mannequin.
- Leaving the flying arena.
- Failing in transmitting data to the MK:DataHub.

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List of Figures

Figure 1.a - Starship robots delivering food in the MK centre. © Copyright Mart Rootamm.

Figure 1.b - Drone services for the Flying High Challenge. © Copyright Sam Churchill.

Figure 2 - Floorplan of the the Centre:MK shopping mall. Source <https://www.centremk.com/>.

Figure 3.a - Middleton Hall area. Source <http://www.mkinnovates.co.uk>.

Figure 3.b - Middleton Hall adjacent allées. © Copyright Lewis Clarke.

Appendix 1 – Results of Expression of Interest

The 12 episodes sketched in this Deliverable have been distributed to several mailing lists of robotics researchers asking for Expression of Interest (EOI), i.e., feedback about the episode goals and possible interest for the research group to form a team and compete in the Smart City competition in such episodes.

The table below summarizes the results of this investigation.

No	Robot owners	Episodes												Past experience
		1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	
27	21	13	14	13	15	15	6	10	6	5	8	6	7	19

From the data collected it is possible to see how most of the applicants had previous experience in robot competitions and they plan to participating using their own robots. Given the broader application, the HRI&mobility category was the most preferred, therefore two episode were selected. Each other category is represented by a single episode.

Geographically, most of the teams come from European countries, reasonably, since the competition will be held in UK. However, there are few application from North America and India.

On average, team composition is more toward five or more components. This information will be taken in account during the logistic organization of the competition.

Several meetings among the partners were spent to select 5 out of these 12 episodes for the actual competition in MK, considering maximization of team participation and distribution of the benchmarked functionalities within the episodes. As a result of this activity, the following 5 episodes were selected

(E03) Delivering coffee shop orders

(E04) Take the elevator

(E07) Serving goodies

(E10) Open the door

(E12) Fast delivery of emergency pills

The rulebooks of these episode have been developed as described in Appendix 2 in this Deliverable.

Appendix 2 – Rulebooks of selected episodes

For the selected episodes, as indicated in Appendix 1, a Technical Committee (TC) for each episode was formed including experts in the research fields of interest for the episode. TC jointly worked to write the rulebook of the episode, also collecting feedback from other TCs, SciRoc partners, and potential teams that submitted an EOI.

The final result of this activity has been the definition of the rulebooks of the selected episodes that will be used for the competition in MK.

The five rulebooks are presented in the following of this document. Below we report the list of contributors.

- **Episode 3** (Lead: IST, others involved: UNIROMA1, OU). The technical committee is composed by Meysam Basiri (IST, leader) and Pedro Lima (IST), Daniele Nardi (UNIROMA1), Italy; and Gianluca Bardaro (OU). The technical committee consulted Alessandro Saffiotti (Örebro University, Sweden) as external expert, to have comments and notes to the episode rulebook definition.
- **Episode 4** (Lead: UNIROMA1, others involved: OU). The technical committee is composed by Luca Iocchi (UNIROMA1, leader), Andrea Marrella (UNIROMA1), Lun Wang (UNIROMA1), and Gianluca Bardaro (OU). The technical committee consulted Mary Ellen Foster (University of Glasgow, UK) as external expert, to have comments and notes to the episode rulebook definition.
- **Episode 7** (Lead: UNIROMA1, others involved: BRSU, OU). The technical committee is composed by Roberto Capobianco (leader, UNIROMA1), Daniele Nardi, (UNIROMA1), Gerhard Kraetzschmar (UBN), Gianluca Bardaro (OU).
- **Episode 10** (Lead: POLIMI, others involved: UNIROMA1, OU). The technical committee is composed by Giulio Fontana (POLIMI, leader), Matteo Matteucci (POLIMI), Francesco Riccio (UNIROMA1), and Gianluca Bardaro (OU). The technical committee consulted Victor López (PAL Robotics, Spain) as external expert, to have comments and notes to the episode rulebook definition.
- **Episode 12** (Lead: CATEC, others involved: UNIROMA1, OU). The technical committee is composed by Francisco J. Perez Grau (CATEC, leader), Antidio Viguria (CATEC), Ciro Potena (UNIROMA1), and Gianluca Bardaro (OU). The technical committee consulted Davide Scaramuzza (University of Zurich, Switzerland) as external expert, to have comments and notes to the episode rulebook definition.

Episode 3

Deliver coffee shop orders

Technical Committee

Meysam Basiri, Instituto Superior Técnico, Portugal

Pedro Lima, Instituto Superior Técnico, Portugal

Daniele Nardi, Sapienza University of Rome, Italy

Gianluca Bardaro, The Open University, UK

External Expert: Alessandro Saffiotti, Örebro University, Sweden

1. General Description

In this episode the robot will assist the staff of a coffee shop to take care of their customers. The robot is asked to recognize the status of all tables inside the shop, report the number of free tables, take orders from the unserved customers and deliver objects to and from the customers' tables.

2. Main scientific challenge

This episode aims at benchmarking some of the key functionalities required by an autonomous service robot to operate inside a restaurant or coffee shop. The main functionalities evaluated here are **people perception** and **object perception**. However, additional side functionalities such as navigation and speech recognition are also required to successfully execute the episode.

Recent advancements in social service robots has led to the introduction of robots in public places such as shopping malls or restaurants for interaction with customers. Several studies have already demonstrated the positive impression of customers when assisted by service robots [1,2,3]. Service robots can approach and interact with customers without causing or receiving social stress [4]. Catering service robots for restaurants and shops has been the topic of multiple research work [5,6,7]. The effectiveness of such robots is currently demonstrated with the rise of robot waitering systems in the market. A catering robot can assist human servers at peak hours by handling the manual works at a fast pace and reducing the customer response time.

Over the past years, in the context of the RoboCup@Home competition and of the European Robotics League - Consumer Service Robots (ERL Consumer), multiple benchmarks were defined which evaluated the performance of people perception and object perception of service robots operating inside domestic environments. In particular, the Restaurant test in RoboCup@Home [9], performed since 2012, aimed at benchmarking

solutions for a service robot to learn a new environment, receive orders from customers and deliver such orders. This test mostly focussed on manipulation, on-line mapping and human-robot interaction. Through the definition of the present episode for the SciRoc smart city competition, we aim at steering and improving the existing contributions of teams on people and object perception. The SciRoc episode will also provide a dynamic and uncertain environment represented by a public space populated by naive users. Teams participating in the ERL Consumer and RoboCup@Home competitions are expected to be able to directly benefit from their existing solutions and experience to successfully showcase their robots in a real coffee-shop-like environment.

3. Platforms allowed

A mobile service robot that is equipped with a tray, a planar surface or any other way of transporting a few small items (such as a cup of coffee, glass of water, mug, small plate with cake, etc) is required. No manipulators are needed for this episode as objects are placed on to the mobile tray by the coffee shop staff and customers. In addition, robots must have a noticeable emergency stop button to shut off all motors in case of an emergency.

4. Scenario Setup

An arena representing an ordinary coffeeshop, consisting of multiple tables and chairs, will be used. It will contain a minimum number of 6 tables to accommodate customers and 1 counter for the staff to place and remove objects. A minimum area of approximately 45 m² is expected for this episode, however, the actual required dimensions might differ based on the size of the furniture used for the episode. The actual number of tables and chairs along with the detailed floor plan and shop dimensions are communicated to the teams before the competition. Each of the tables will have a unique identification number.

Figure1: Example of a possible layout of tables and customers for a trial of the episode.

Common tableware and merchandise found at ordinary coffee shops will be used as the objects to be perceived and carried by the robots. Objects can contain actual liquid in them such as a cup of coffee or a glass of water. The detailed description of all objects will be provided to the participating teams 3-4 weeks before the competition and the actual objects are provided to the teams during the setup days. A menu will be placed on all the tables for the visiting customers which will contain the list of all items that can be ordered.

For every trial of the episode, an unknown number of volunteers acting as coffee shop customers are randomly seated at different tables. The volunteers can compose of team members, members of the technical or organization committee or general public upon filling a consent form. The number of people and their locations are randomly generated by the referees with the help of a random generator right before the trial begins.

5. MK Data Hub Interaction

The Milton Keynes city hosting the competition is equipped with a data acquisition and management infrastructure (MK:DataHub) consisting of live sensors that reflect different aspects of the functionalities of the city (transport, environment, energy, water, etc.). The data gathered by the robots in this episode, such as the coffee shop status perceived by the robot with the number of available tables inside the shop can be communicated automatically to the infrastructure to contribute to the smart city data platform. Teams are notified before the competition by the competition organizers about the data and communication protocols.

6. Procedure

This section describes the step by step procedure for a complete trial of the episode. A single trial consists of three phases that are executed sequentially without any interruption. A robot can automatically proceed to the next phase at any time if it is unable to execute or fully complete a phase. The robot must announce the start of a new phase and the robot's objective before execution of a task to allow the referee and the audience to better understand its behaviour.

Preparations and start of the trial

- The robot is positioned at the starting location, near the counter.
- Several volunteers acting as customers will enter the shop and are randomly seated at different tables by the referee.
- A restaurant employee (played by a member of the OC/TC), will take and deliver the orders for some of the tables and soon realizes that it requires help with other tables.
- The trial begins at the scheduled time, when the employee asks the robot for assistance. The start signal can be either a single press of a button on the robot or a simple voice command.

Phase 1: Recognizing the shop's status

- The robot starts by navigating around to recognize the status of all the tables at the shop. For every table, the robot must identify and announce through speech the following information:
 - 1) the table's status:
 - a) Needs serving: The table has customers but no objects on the table.
 - b) Already served: The table contains both customers and objects.
 - c) Needs cleaning: The table has objects but no customers.
 - d) Ready: The table is ready to accept new customers, i.e. no objects and no customers.
 - 2) The number of customers at the table, if any.

In addition to speech, the table's status and number of customers per table must be stored on to a text file on the robot. The referee will request the file to be examined, if needed, after the termination of the trial. Additionally, teams are requested to communicate this info automatically to the MK digital hub.

Phase 2: Serving an order

- The robot approaches one of the tables that is waiting to be served. Alternatively, if the robot was unable to correctly identify the shop's status in Phase 1, it can wait to receive a waving gesture from one of the customers before approaching to that table.
- The robot asks the customers of the table to select their orders from the menu. (3 items will be selected). As HRI is not the main focus of the episode, this selection procedure is left open for the teams to decide and can be anything as simple as asking the customers to communicate the item numbers through speech, QR code, or to click on the items from a user interface display on the robot.¹
- Once the order is placed, the robot navigates to the counter and communicates the order to the assistant behind the counter. The order is then placed on the counter by the assistant with one of the items missing or being incorrect.
- The robot must identify the wrong/missing item and ask for the correction.
- The order is then placed on the robot's tray and the robot must deliver it to the correct table.
- The customers pick the items and the robot moves back to the default location.

Phase 3: Greeting and guiding a new customer to the table

- A new customer will enter the shop and will wait to be guided to a table.
- The robot must automatically detect the presence of the new customer in the shop, approach and greet the customer, and then guide the customer to a ready table.
- The robot moves back to the default location indicating the end of the trial.

¹ A natural human-robot interaction is preferred and is expected to draw the attention of the general audience/volunteers who will be determining the award of "Best Robot by Audience".

7. Timing

The maximum allowed time for a single trial is 15 minutes. The time stops when the robot moves back to its default location and announces that it has completed the trial. Note that the trial execution time is an important element in this episode and faster solutions are considered to be better in case of ties in the number of achievements.

The participating teams must have their robots ready in the default location sharply at the time communicated in the schedule. After 2 minutes from the scheduled time, the referee will start the test, i.e. s/he starts the timer (no delays for any reason). If the robot is still not ready, there will be no penalty but the time will run on. During this period the team can start the test at any moment, but the end time will not be postponed.

Within the first 5 minutes from the start of the trial, the team can request for a restart. In this case the team is allowed to enter the arena, position the robot back on the default location and perform any operation on the robot. The restart can be done only once for each trial. Any score achieved before the restart will be canceled and the time will not be stopped during the restart procedure.

8. Score

Achievements

- The robot correctly reports all the tables that need serving.
- The robot correctly reports the status of all the tables.
- The robot correctly reports the number of customers for all tables with customers.
- The robot reaches an unserved table and asks for the order.
- The robot correctly understands and informs the order of the customer to the counter.
- The robot correctly recognizes the wrong or missing item and corrects the order.
- The robot delivers the order to the right table.
- The robot detects and greets the new customer entering the shop.
- The robot guides the customer to a ready table.

Penalizing behaviors

- The robot hits any of the furniture and objects. (one penalty for each hit)
- The objects on the tray drop or spill due to the movement of the robot
- The robot requires multiple repetition of the speech command

Disqualifying behaviors

The episode is immediately stopped and any score achieved so far will be canceled if:

- The robot hits a human.
- The robot hits and damages the furniture and/or objects.

Competition Stages and the Final scores

The competition is arranged in two stages: 1) Competition Days, 2) Final. The top 3 teams in the ranking of the Competition Days qualify for the final to be held on the last day of the competition. The final ranking for assigning the first, second and third place will be determined by the performance in the final. During the competition days, several runs will be available to each team (let this number be M). Notice that M is the number of slots available for each team, it may differ from the actual number of performances of each team, if teams are not ready to attend some runs. During the Final, only one run will be performed.

Aggregate score of the Competition days. The aggregate score for each team for the M episodes performed during the Competition days will be determined according to the score system of the European Robotics League as follows:

- select the best N trials of the team
- determine the median of the scores of the N trials selected.

Let n be the position of the median in the ordered list of team scores, i.e., $n = (N + 1) / 2$ (when N is odd), then N (and consequently n) are determined according to the number of episodes scheduled M , according to the following table

M	N	n
6-9	5	3
10-12	7	4
13-15	9	5

In case of tie score for the access to the Final, the policy for tie breaking is described below. If such policy does not break the tie, all teams with the same score will enter the Final.

The policy for tie braking is:

- average task completion time for the first n-1 highest scores

Best Social Robot

Apart from the above scoring system which is used to determine the rankings for the best robot in this episode, we will collect questionnaires from the general public who volunteer in the episode to determine an extra award for the “most social robot”. A questionnaire will be used for this purpose:

	5 Yes, very much	4 Yes, a little	3 Neutral	2 No, not much	1 No, not at all	Not Applicable
Have you perceived friendness interacting with robot?						
Have you perceived social relationships with robot?						
Have you perceived enough safety while interacting with robot?						
Have you perceived a feeling of ease (comfortable) interacting with robot?						
Could you understand well when the robot was talking?						
Did the robot face the person whom it was interacting with during this episode?						
Do you feel the robot’s distance during interaction was suitable?						
Was it easy to communicate your order to the robot?						

9. Detailed instructions for referees

The referees/organizers must prepare a schedule to ensure an equal access of the arena to the participating teams for the setup days. Also they must make sure that all objects on the menu are provided to the teams during the setup days for training purposes. The referees must check the robots and approve their safety mechanism before the actual trials of the competition.

Once the arena has been built, and before allowing the teams to access the arena, the referees must mark the location of all tables, wall partitions and other furniture to ensure they are placed back on their default locations for the actual trials.

A competition schedule for the competition trials must be prepared in advance.

Time slots of 20 minutes (15 minute trials + 5 minutes of preparation and team exchange) is expected for every trial. Each team must be given an equal opportunity to perform multiple trials (minimum 3 to maximum 9 trials based on the time availability and the number of participating teams).

A minimum number of two referees and up to 10 volunteers acting as customers are required for execution of the test. The referees are expected to carefully study the rules and procedure of the benchmark before the competition. The volunteers will be selected from the members of the teams and other interested audience. When using a member of the general public, a consensus form must be given to them prior to the trial and a user evaluation form is to be given to them after the trial. Referees should try to initialize the scenario before the trial and assign roles to all volunteers. The roles that require interaction with the robot, for example the customer to be served or the new customer entering the shop, should be assigned to the general audience as they are the ones filling the user-evaluation forms.

For every trial, the referees must prepare the scenario according to the description provided in the "Procedures" section by distributing a random number of customers (between 5 to 10 customers) and some objects (from the list of possible objects) on the tables. The distribution difficulty among different trials must not vary significantly.

To begin a trial, one of the referees can stand at the counter. He/she has the responsibility of starting and stopping the benchmark, keeping track of the time and placing and removing the objects from the counter. The second referee will always maintain a distance behind the robot, ensuring the safe operation of the robot at all times and scoring the achievements and penalties using the provided score sheets.

At the end of a trial the referees cross check the score with each other, record the execution time on the score sheet, and confirm the score with the team leader of the participating team.

10. Detailed instructions for teams

Teams need to show the safety mechanisms of their robots and to demonstrate their use once before the competition begins. They also need to communicate to the organizers the required information for operating the robot. For example, how should the referee start the robot, what is the preferred method of human-robot interaction, how to speak to the robot or how to use the robot's user interface to input orders and where/how to place objects on the robot.

During the competition, teams must prepare their robots outside the arena and can only enter the arena at the assigned times. They must follow the schedule of the trial and comply with the timings described in the "Timing" section. Once the referee signals the end of the trial, the participating team must immediately remove the robot from the arena to allow the next team to enter.

Teams are kindly requested to log and store the robot's Internal data for every trial and to provide it to the organizers after the end of trials. This data will not be used during the competition, but it is used to produce and publish datasets for the benefit of the robotics community. This data must be expressed in the reference frame of the test bed which will be clearly marked on it. There are no restrictions about the framerate and data can be saved at the rate they are acquired or produced. Only data relevant to the episode is expected to be logged and can be in the format of rosbag, in particular the following data is expected to be logged:

1. Images processed for object perception and the calibration info for the images
2. point cloud used to recognize an object
3. The audio signals of the conversation with the customers/staff.
4. The 2D robot pose at the floor level and trajectories planned by the robot
5. Laser scans and odometry used for estimating the pose.
6. tf topics on the robot.

11. Ethical issues

Volunteers involved in the episode, to act as customers, will be selected by the referees among team members, members of TC/OC or adult customers in the MK shopping mall. In case of using real customers from the mall they will be informed about the episode, its procedure, how to interact with the robot for communicating the order and about the safety procedures.

The customers will be invited to sign a consensus form where they declare to have been informed about the above mentioned information and that they volunteer to participate in the episode.

12. Safety procedures

Teams are responsible to describe safety procedures of the robots used during the challenge. A document describing such procedures and risk analysis must be submitted at registration time and will be used by referee at any time to guarantee safety when using the robot and to instruct customers participating to the episode.

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Appendix A. Score sheet

Team: _____

Execution Time: _____

Trial number: _____

Achievements:

- The robot correctly reports the tables that need serving.
- The robot correctly reports the status of all the tables.
- The robot correctly reports the number of customers for all tables with customers.
- The robot detects and reaches an unserved table asking for the order.
- The robot correctly understands and communicates the order to the counter.
- The robot correctly recognizes the wrong or missing item and corrects the order.
- The robot delivers the order to the right table.
- The robot detects and greets the new customer entering the shop.
- The robot guides the customer to an unoccupied table.

Penalizing behaviors:

- The robot hits any of the furniture and objects. Number of hits: _____
- The objects on the tray drop or spill due to the movement of the robot
- The robot requires multiple repetition of commands/answers

Disqualifying behaviors:

- The robot hits a human.
- The robot damages objects and furniture

Notes:

Appendix B. Referee/audience application:

This section describes some of the recommended features for the referee application and the display for the audience.

Referee's interface:

- Checklist showing the preparation steps needed before starting the trial (Section 9)
- Menu to select the team's name and the trial number
- Timer showing the execution time
- Button to start the trial/timer
- Possibility to select the phase number and robot's current objective
- Possibility to tick/cross the table state and customer number results for each table.
- List of achievements and penalties to tick or cross.

Public interface:

- Team name and trial number
- Current phase and objective of the robot
- Results for estimation of the table's status and the number of customers per table
- List of achievements with the next aimed achievement highlighted
- Current score and time

Team: <u>Robot XXX</u>		Trial: <u>3</u>															
Current objective of robot: 2. Taking the order of a customer		Achievements: <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Reporting the tables that need serving. <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Reporting the status of all the tables <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Reporting the number of customers for all tables <div style="border: 1px dashed black; padding: 2px;"> <input type="checkbox"/> Reaching an unserved table and taking the order. </div> <input type="checkbox"/> Understands and communicating the order <input type="checkbox"/> Recognizing the wrong item in the order <input type="checkbox"/> Delivering the order to the correct table <input type="checkbox"/> Detecting and greeting the new customer <input type="checkbox"/> Guiding the customer to an unoccupied table															
KTR Estimation of the table's status: 																	
Estimation of No. of customers: <table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Table</th> <th>1</th> <th>2</th> <th>3</th> <th>4</th> <th>5</th> <th>6</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>Result</td> <td>✓</td> <td>✗</td> <td>✓</td> <td>✗</td> <td>✓</td> <td>✓</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>		Table	1	2	3	4	5	6	Result	✓	✗	✓	✗	✓	✓	Score: Time: A: 1 P:0 05:00	
Table	1	2	3	4	5	6											
Result	✓	✗	✓	✗	✓	✓											

Figure 2: Example of the display to show the status of the episode to the public

Episode 4

Take the elevator

Technical Committee

Luca Iocchi, Sapienza University of Rome, Italy

Andrea Marrella, Sapienza University of Rome, Italy

Lun Wang, Sapienza University of Rome, Italy

Gianluca Bardaro, The Open University, UK

External Expert: Mary Ellen Foster, University of Glasgow, UK

1. General Description

The robot must take the elevator crowded with customers to reach a service located in another floor. The robot should interact with the MK:DataHub to discover which floor it must reach to accomplish its task. The robot must be able to take the elevator together with regular customers of the shopping mall. The robot should be able to enter and exit the elevator at the right floor in the presence of people nearby and/or inside. To perform the episode the robot can interact with the customers in spoken language. The robot is not supposed to push buttons and it can ask the people around to do it.

2. Main scientific challenge

The main functionality tested in this episode is *Navigation respecting proxemics* when robot interacts with customers; other required functionalities are Spoken Dialogue beyond command interpretation and people detection [1]. Several studies have been presented on navigation functionality for accessing an elevator. For example, during AAI Robot Challenge in 2002, a portion of the competition task was riding an elevator, developers demonstrated techniques to perceive elevators from laser scans, and system users a feature-based recognizer to detect elevators [2]. In 2012, the competition RoboCup@Home included a navigation task to follow a person into an elevator in order to reach a final destination in another floor of the venue [14]. Evaluation of the test was given by reaching check-points in the environment. In this RoboCup@Home task the focus was on navigation and person following, while Human-Robot interaction was limited to giving commands to the robot and social navigation was not a specific focus of the test.

The SciRoc Episode “Take the elevator” has a different focus with respect to previous competition tasks including social navigation and mixed evaluation including performance on both robot achievements and user evaluation about human-robot interaction phases.

As for the technical challenges considered in this episode, the path planning algorithms for navigating in narrow spaces like an elevator have been studied for long time (e.g., [3]). How to perform interactive tasks into an elevator, the approach towards designing the individual components with a focus on machine vision and how to integrate the individual components into one coherent autonomous task-oriented behavior have also been studied in the past [4,5]. The performance evaluation used in these works was not applied to any scientific competition.

On the other hand, Human-Robot-Interaction (HRI) user’s study on proxemics has shown that, when the robot asks for help to people, the personal space distance seems to be the most comfortable for humans [6], but some authors claimed that there is no need to study proxemics for the robot to navigate through a crowd if it is the last one to exit and the first one to enter the elevator [7]. Analyzing safety issues during physical HRI is also important because safety issues can impact user’s evaluation [8,9]. For the spoken functionality and people detection, gaze can have a positive impact interacting with customers [10].

Typical general-purpose evaluation techniques in HRI are: Godspeed questionnaire [11], Robotic Social Attributes Scale (RoSAS) [12] and Negative Attitudes of People toward Robots (NARS) [13]. However, to the best of our knowledge, no previous work is available on user evaluation of robot social navigation and in particular of the scenario where a robot shares the space inside an elevator with people.

Thus, SciRoc episode “Take the elevator” contributes in benchmarking social navigation abilities of robots in a public environment populated by naive users. The benchmark proposed in this Episode includes a mixed evaluation taking into account both robot performances in proceeding towards its goal (reaching a given location of an environment placed at a different floor with respect to the starting location) and user evaluation of the Human-Robot Interaction phases happening during the task.

3. Platforms allowed

This episode is open to any robot that can navigate and interact with people in spoken language. The size of the robot must be suitable to access an elevator door. The robot should be easily moved in and out the competition scenario, even when not in function, by maximum two team members with minimum effort.

The robot must be provided with a clearly visible **emergency button** that can be pressed at any time by any person involved in the episode (referees, users, team members, etc.). Upon pressing the emergency button, the robot should immediately stop executing any motion with any moving parts. Teams must provide a document describing safety procedures and risk analysis for the use of their robot and any other equipment used during the challenge (see Section 12).

Robot inspection will be performed to test safety devices and procedures before the runs of the competition. No robot is allowed to participate in any test if safety procedures are not completed. Teams have to guarantee that safety devices and procedures are always working and enabled. Referees can check safety procedures at any time during the competition.

4. Scenario Setup

The episode takes place in an area reproducing the space in front of an elevator. The elevator is built as a cabin with a door with typical sizes of elevators in MK centre.

Customers will interact with the robot during the episode, as described in Section 6. Customers are chosen from the visitors of the competition after a clearance check, where they accept to take the elevator with the robot, and to fill-in a questionnaire upon termination of the episode.

The total area of the episode will be approximately 8 x 8 m. The scenario includes a start area (2 x 1.5 m), an elevator cabin (2 x 2 m) and a finish area (2 x 1.5 m). The elevator cabin is formed by solid and opaque material. Start and finish areas are delimited with markers on the ground. In every test, the robot starts from the start area, enters and exits the elevator, and then reaches the finish area. The elevator will be provided by a sliding door. The opening will be between 80 cm and 100 cm wide and 200 cm high. The elevator will be equipped with a video camera showing to the audience the episode in progress. This video camera will not be accessible to the robot.

The following figure shows the layout of the scenario

Figure 1. Scenario layout.

The scenario includes a preparation area (about 2 x 2 meters) that is reserved for the team that is about to start the next episode. Within this area any action on the robot is allowed and no score can be gained. The robot has to autonomously exit the preparation area to start the test. As soon as a robot exits the preparation area, it cannot re-enter it. The team has to clear this area as soon as possible, while the robot is performing the episode and the area can be occupied by the next team to start setup for the next run.

5. MK Data Hub Interaction

The DataHub will provide the location of shops and services in terms of the floor where they are located. Upon the request of achieving a goal, that will be entered by the referee, the

robot will receive from the DH the floor in which the task must be accomplished and actively operate to reach such a floor.

Protocol definition and software instructions to communicate with the MK DataHub will be provided in a separate document.

6. Procedure and rules

The episode will include between 3 and 5 adult customers selected by the referees randomly, notice that subjects in general will have no experience interacting with a social robot.

Two of these persons will participate only in the Encounter situation and between one and three persons will enter the elevator with the robot.

The number of people participating in each run will not be provided to teams before the run of the episode, so the robot has to figure out how many people are involved.

6.1 Expected behavior of the robot

The episode starts at the scheduled time, as explained in Section 7. When the robot leaves the Start area, it can request to the MK DataHub its target goal (in particular, the floor to be reached). Protocol definition and software instructions to communicate with the MK DataHub will be provided in a separate document. Then the robot must reach the elevator and reach the requested floor. The robot should move in the area near the elevator where people are standing to take the elevator. The robot announces its intention of taking the elevator and then interacts with the customers to enter and exit at the right floor. After exiting the elevator, the robot will move away from the elevator towards the finish area.

Phase 1: Moving to the elevator (see Figure 2)

In the first phase, the robot moves from the start area to the elevator. The Encounter Situation may happen during this phase (see below).

Figure 2. Phase 1 assuming 5 people and encounter situation happening during Phase 1

Phase 2: Entering/exiting the elevator (see Figure 3)

The area just in front of the elevator is occupied by an unknown number of standing people (between 1 and 3). When the robot reaches the elevator, it has to place at a proper location outside it depending on the location of other people. The robot has to clearly specify when it considers to be arrived at a position waiting for the elevator doors to open, for example through speech. Elevator doors are operated by the Referee after the robot signal that it has reached its desired location outside the elevator. If the robot does not announce its arrival, but it remains still for more than 30 seconds in a proper position (as judged by the Referee), the Referee will open the elevator doors anyway attempting to continue the episode. When the elevator door opens, the robot has to wait until all the people around enters the door, then it can move and enter the door occupying a proper space in the elevator cabin. The robot has to face one person within the elevator cabin, declare which floor it desires to

go, and ask for confirmation that the proper floor has been selected. When the door opens again, the robot is allowed to ask to one person (while facing him/her) which is the current floor. If the current floor is the destination one for the robot, it must exit, otherwise, it must stay. In case the robot has to exit, it must negotiate with people in the elevator who is going first. Preferably, the robot has to yield to humans, unless it is in a situation in which it is blocking the door: in this case it will move first. In case the robot has to stay in the elevator, in general it should not move, unless it is in a situation in which it is blocking the door: in this case it may announce and perform the actions of exiting the elevator, waiting for people to exit as well and then re-entering.

The door may open several times before reaching the robot's target floor. Door opening is operated by the referees, who will give enough time to the robot to assess the situation and interact with customers inside it.

Customers can exit at any floor (including the target floor of the robot) as instructed by the referees, in an order that is unknown to the robot. There will be always a person in the elevator when the robot has to get out. No other customer will enter the elevator after the initial entering step.

Figure 3. Phase 2 assuming 5 people in the episode (3 in the elevator)

Phase 3: moving from the elevator to finish area (see Figure 4)

In Phase 3, the robot will move from the elevator to the finish area. The Encounter Situation may happen during this phase (see below).

Figure 4. Phase 3 (with encounter situation happening during Phase 1)

Encounter Situation: encounter persons while moving (see Figure 2)

During either Phase 1 or Phase 3 (at team choice and only once), the robot will encounter two persons: Person A is standing in a location and s/he is not interested to interact with the robot, Person B is actively moving towards the robot willing to interact with it.

The expected behavior of the robot is to not interact with Person A and to interact with Person B. With respect to Person A (i.e., when the robot detects a person who is not interested in interacting), the robot will just avoid him/her and proceed without any attempt to communicate. With respect to Person B (i.e., when the robot detects a person who is interested in interacting), the robot will have to stop moving, face the person, tell its name and communicate its intention to reach the target floor. Any additional interaction between the robot and Person B is allowed as for team choice. It is not necessary for the robot to answer questions from Person B, but it is also not forbidden, so teams can decide for a longer more complex interaction.

The location of Person A, the path of Person B and the order in which the two persons are encountered are unknown to the robot.

Persons A and B will not participate in other phases of the test, in particular, they will not enter the elevator.

Note: By default, the encounter situation will happen during Phase 1. If a team prefers to have encounters happening during Phase 3, team leader has to communicate this choice to the referees before the start of the episode (see Section 10).

6.2 General rules

At any time during the episode, the robot can receive instructions about its position from the participants, such as “move left/right forward/backward”, “move away”, “you should not stay here”, etc. If correctly interpreted, these instructions can be used to reach some achievement with penalties. Teams should not expect anyway that users will drive the robot to proper locations with this mechanism.

Team members are not allowed to give any of these instructions to the robot at any time during the episode. Team members are not allowed to ask users to give any of these instructions at any time.

6.3 Team information

The scenario in which the episode will run will be available during the setup days. Any mapping procedure can be performed, no major changes will be applied during the competition.

6.4 Team choices

Teams can communicate to referee, at least 30 minutes before the start of the run, if they want the Encounter situation to happen during Phase 3 (by default it will happen during Phase 1).

7. Timing

All the tests will start at the time communicated in the schedule and will end after the duration of the test. During this period the team can start the test at any moment, but the end time will not be postponed if the team is not ready to start in time.

The duration of the episode for each team is 10 minutes. During this time slot, the team may attempt only one run of the episode. If a robot cannot start the episode (i.e., leave the Start area) within the first 4 minutes of the time slot, it will be asked to be moved away.

In any case, the Start area must be cleared within the first 4 minutes of the slot assigned to each team. After the robot exits the Start area, teams have to clear the area immediately removing any other equipment (laptops, power cords, etc.). The robot is not allowed to re-enter the Start area after it exits it.

At least 6 runs of the episode will be scheduled. Two examples of possible schedule with multiple runs depending on the number of participating teams are provided below.

Example 1: 6 teams 12 runs

Day 1	Day 2	Day 3
10.00-11.00 Run 1	10.00-11.00 Run 5	10.00-11.00 Run 9
12.00-13.00 Run 2	12.00-13.00 Run 6	12.00-13.00 Run 10
14.00-15.00 Run 3	14.00-15.00 Run 7	14.00-15.00 Run 11
16.00-17.00 Run 4	16.00-17.00 Run 8	16.00-17.00 Run 12

Example 2: 9 teams 9 runs

Day 1	Day 2	Day 3
10.00-11.30 Run 1	10.00-11.30 Run 4	10.00-11.30 Run 7
12.30-14.00 Run 2	12.30-14.00 Run 5	12.30-14.00 Run 8
15.00-16.30 Run 3	15.00-16.30 Run 6	15.00-16.30 Run 9

The order of participant teams will rotate, so each team will start the same number of times in any order.

8. Score

The score of the episode is determined by two sets of achievements: one based on objective measures, another one based on users' evaluation. User evaluation will be collected through questionnaires as explained in the next section.

8.1 Filling questionnaires

After the episode all three to five customers involved in the episode will fill the questionnaire described below. A questionnaire is valid (i.e., will be considered for scoring) only if it contains more than 50% of valid answers.

Questionnaire E4 Take the Elevator

Thanks a lot for your participating in the performance of the task Episode 4 - Take the Elevator.

Please fill out the following questionnaire, the results of which will be used for research purposes in the field of robotics.

Please fill in the following information regarding your personal data.

Gender	M	F
Age		

After you have interacted or observed the robotic behaviors in E4, please select one from each 5-point likert-scale. **If the behavior is not possible to evaluate, just leave the blank.**

Social Behavior of robot

	Absolutely Yes (5)	Yes (4)	Neutral (3)	No (2)	Absolutely No (1)
Have you perceived happiness of the robot?					
Have you perceived sociability of the robot?					
Have you perceived capability of the robot?					
Have you perceived responsiveness of the robot?					
Have you perceived interactiveness of the robot?					
Have you perceived naturalness of the robot?					

Proxemics between human and robot

	Absolutely Yes (5)	Yes (4)	Neutral (3)	No (2)	Absolutely No (1)
Did robot look at users' face during the conversation between user and the robot?					
Did user look at the robot's face during the conversation between user and the robot?					
Have users paid attention to the conversation with the robot?					
Have users understood well the meaning of conversation?					
Have you perceived consciousness of the robot?					
Have you perceived friendliness of the robot?					
Have you perceived politeness of the robot?					
Have you perceived adaptability of the robot?					
Have you perceived ease of use with the robot?					

Collaboration with robot

	Absolutely Yes (5)	Yes (4)	Neutral (3)	No (2)	Absolutely No (1)
Have you perceived enjoyment of the robot?					
Have you perceived collaborativeness of the robot?					

8.2 Achievements

- The robot properly deals with Person A (avoidance, no interaction).
- The robot properly deals with Person B (interaction).
- The robot enters the elevator.
- The robot declares the target floor to Person C.
- The robot exits the elevator at the proper floor.
- The robot reaches the finish area. Above (\geq) 80 % of positive user's perception (≥ 4) over total valid answers.

8.3 Penalising behaviours

- Robot motion requires a person to move away to avoid a collision (repeatable).
- A user instructs the robot to move away from one location (repeatable).
- The robot misunderstands users' requests.
- The robot obstructs the way to the customers.
- Above (\geq) 80 % of negative user's perception (≤ 2) over total valid answers.

8.4 Disqualifying behaviours

The episode is immediately stopped and any score achieved so far is canceled.

- The robot hits a human.
- The robot hits and damages the furniture and/or objects.
- Team members give instructions to the robot during the episode or ask users to do it.

8.5 Overall score

The competition is arranged in two stages: 1) Competition Days, 2) Final. The top 3 teams in the ranking of the Competition Days qualify for the final to be held in the last day of the competition. The final ranking for assigning the first, second and third place will be determined by the performance in the Final. During the Competition Days, several runs will be available to each team (let this number be M). Notice that M is the number of slots available for each team, it may differ from the actual number of performances of each team, if teams are not ready to attend some runs. During the Final, only one run will be performed.

Aggregate score of the Competition Days. The aggregate score for each team for the M episodes performed during the Competition Days will be determined according to the score system of the European Robotics League as follows:

- select the best N trials of the team

- determine the median of the scores of the N trials selected.

Let n be the position of the median in the ordered list of team scores, i.e., $n = (N + 1) / 2$ (when N is odd), then N (and consequently n) are determined according to the number of scheduled episodes M , according to the following table:

M	N	n
6-9	5	3
10-12	7	4
13-15	9	5

In case of tie score for the access to the Final, the policy for tie breaking is described below. If such policy does not break the tie, all teams with the same score will enter the Final.

The policy for tie breaking will be:

- average of first $n-1$ highest scores
- average of next $n-1$ highest scores after the median (i.e. n -th highest score)

In case of tie score again, the rank will be the same.

9. Detailed instructions for referees

Choose 3 to 5 people participating in each run. Before the run, explain their role in the episode and collect consensus for video recording. After the run, illustrate the questionnaires and collect the results.

Choose location of people:

- Person A (standing in the path)
- Person B (moving in the path towards the robot with intention to interact)
- Person C_1, \dots, C_n ($n=1..3$) (location around the elevator and which floors will exit)

Choose the target service (i.e., the target floor of the robot) and the sequence of floors visited by the elevator. The sequence is chosen in such a way that the target floor for the robot will not be the first one visited.

10. Detailed instructions for teams

Teams have to be aware of the schedule, where the time slots assigned to them are listed. Teams should be available around the episode arena about 10 minutes before the start of their time slot, without providing obstruction to other teams. Teams can enter the Start area 5 minutes before the time slot to prepare the robot. The episode can start at the time in which it is scheduled by just letting the robot leave autonomously the Start area.

The robot can start the episode (i.e., leave the Start area) at any time, but the time of the episode is fixed in the schedule and does not depend on the robot actions.

If the robot is not able to leave the Start area within the first 4 minutes of the time slot available to the team, the team will have to give up the run and clear the Start area immediately.

The test finishes at the scheduled time (i.e., 10 minutes after the scheduled start). When the episode ends, team have to remove the robot from the arena within 2 minutes, exiting through the Finish area.

If team wants to choose the Encounter situation to happen during Phase 2, the team leader has to deliver a Team Information Sheet (Appendix B2) at least 1 hour before the start of the run of the episode.

Summary of team activities assuming time slot starts at time **T0** (in minutes)

1 hour before the run (optional) Give Team Information Sheet to Referees if Encounter situation should happen during Phase 3

T0-10	Approach the arena
T0-5	Enter the Start area
T0	The robot can leave the Start area and start the episode
T0+X	The robot leaves the Start area (X in [0,4])
T0+X+1	Team clears the Start area
T0+4	Time limit for the robot to start the episode
T0+5	Time limit to clear the Start area
T0+10	End of the episode
T0+12	Time limit to leave the arena through the Finish Area

11. Ethical issues

Customers involved in the episode will be selected by referees among adult customers in the MK shopping mall. These customers will be informed about the task under execution and about the safety procedures of the interaction with the robots.

The customers will be invited to sign a consensus form where they declare to have been informed about the above mentioned information and that they volunteer to participate in the episode. They will also give consensus to use data collected during the episode, including the answers of the questionnaires, in an anonymous way for research purposes.

12. Safety procedures

The only moving part of the scenario is the elevator door. A specific safety procedure for the use of the elevator door will be provided by the constructors of the scenario.

Teams are responsible to describe safety procedures of the robots used during the challenge. A document describing such procedures and risk analysis must be submitted at registration time and will be used by referee at any time to guarantee safety when using the robot and to instruct customers participating to the episode.

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Appendix A. Score sheet

Team: _____

Execution Time: _____

Trial number: _____

Achievements:

- The robot properly deals with Person A (avoidance, no interaction).
- The robot properly deals with Person B (interaction).
- The robot enters the elevator.
- The robot declares the target floor to Person C.
- The robot exits the elevator at the proper floor.
- The robot reaches the finish area.
- Above (\geq) 80 % of positive user's perception (≥ 4).

Penalizing behaviors:

- Robot motion requires a person to move away to avoid collision. Number: _____
- A user has to instruct the robot to move away from one location. Number: _____
- The robot misunderstands users' requests.
- The robot obstructs the way to the customers.
- Above (\geq) 80 % of negative user's perception (≤ 2).

Disqualifying behaviors:

- The robot hits a human.
- The robot damages objects and furniture
- Team members give instructions to the robot or ask users to do it.

Notes:

Appendix B. Team information sheets

B1. Referee Choices Sheet (secret to teams)

Nr. of people involved in the episode	<table border="1" style="width: 100%; text-align: center;"> <tr> <td style="width: 33%;">3</td> <td style="width: 33%;">4</td> <td style="width: 33%;">5</td> </tr> </table>			3	4	5																						
3	4	5																										
Robot destination floor	<table border="1" style="width: 100%; text-align: center;"> <tr> <td style="width: 33%; background-color: #cccccc;">1</td> <td style="width: 33%;">2</td> <td style="width: 33%;">3</td> </tr> </table>			1	2	3																						
1	2	3																										
People	<table border="1" style="width: 100%; text-align: center;"> <thead> <tr> <th style="width: 25%;">Name</th> <th style="width: 25%;">Role</th> <th style="width: 25%;">Pos</th> <th style="width: 25%;">Floor</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td></td> <td>A</td> <td></td> <td style="background-color: #cccccc;">1</td> </tr> <tr> <td></td> <td>B</td> <td></td> <td style="background-color: #cccccc;">1</td> </tr> <tr> <td></td> <td>C1</td> <td></td> <td></td> </tr> <tr> <td></td> <td>C2</td> <td></td> <td></td> </tr> <tr> <td></td> <td>C2</td> <td></td> <td></td> </tr> </tbody> </table>				Name	Role	Pos	Floor		A		1		B		1		C1				C2				C2		
Name	Role	Pos	Floor																									
	A		1																									
	B		1																									
	C1																											
	C2																											
	C2																											

Note: at least one person in the elevator when robot has to get out.

B2. Team Information Sheet - from Team to Referees

Team information sheet used by teams to provide information to referees about the execution of the episode.

To be filled and delivered to the main referee at least 1 hour before the run.

Team: _____

Execution Time: _____

Trial number: _____

Encounter situation

Phase 1 (default)	Phase 3
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Possible instructions for the users to interact with the robot (Sect. 6.2)

Appendix C. Referee App and Visualization App

The Referee App will include three functionalities:

1. **goal selection** to choose the target floor for the robot and communicate it to the robot
2. **floor selection** to indicate the current floor of the elevator during the episode
3. **open/close door** to open/close the elevator door

The Visualization App will include visualization for the following elements during the run of the episode: target floor for the robot, current floor of the elevator, and phases of interactions.

Episode 7

Shopping Pick and Pack

Technical Committee

Roberto Capobianco, Sapienza University of Rome, Italy

Daniele Nardi, Sapienza University of Rome, Italy

Gerhard Kraetzschmar, Hochschule Bonn-Rhein-Sieg, Germany

Gianluca Bardaro, The Open University, UK

Duncan Russell, Ocado Technology, UK

Jelizaveta Konstantinova, Ocado Technology, UK

1. General Description

This episode addresses the problem of delivering customized orders. The domain chosen is the operation of a goodies shop. The user (or customer) uses an app on a tablet to select a limited number of items from a range of packaged products, such as a pack of coffee beans, or a jar of honey. An order processing system assigns the task to collect the requested items from the shop shelves and to put them into a delivery area. The robot delivers the product to a delivery area where a person picks it up and moves it to the order pickup desk for the customer.

2. Main Scientific Challenges

The main functionality tested in this episode is *mobile manipulation* of an autonomous robot. In the latest years, mobile manipulation has become a problem of interest among researchers due to the variety and complexity of challenges and robot capabilities that are involved. Different robotic competitions [1-6] have been realized that address this problem, aiming at 1) measuring the performance of these complex systems, 2) defining metrics and assessing benchmarking criteria, 3) fostering research and development of new approaches and technologies, and 4) creating awareness and drawing more attention from the general public to robotics.

For example, in the educational ICRA DJI RoboMaster Mobile Manipulation Challenge [1] teams of students were challenged either to design and develop a self-made lightweight mobile manipulator or to use a standard robot that could autonomously pick, transport, and stack fixed-sized building blocks. The RoCKIn@Work competition [2] defined a more challenging task by increasing the complexity of tasks and variety of objects to manipulate. In particular, teams were required to develop robots autonomously switching between tasks and capable of performing mobile manipulation for assembly processes, quality control, order handling, and logistics. The main objective of the competition consisted in pushing teams to develop new solutions to perception, motion planning and grasping. With respect to

other competitions, RoCKIn adopted a sophisticated approach with multifaceted scoring of both tasks and functionalities. However, all tasks were predefined - without orders coming at execution time - and for each object a CAD model was provided. A similar approach has been recently transferred to RoboCup@Work [4]. Conversely, the Amazon Picking Challenge [5] introduced work orders that were specified offline just prior to each run, while adopting a simple scoring system. The challenge goal consisted in designing an autonomous robot to pick items from warehouse shelves, whose objects belonged to 25 known categories of different sizes. The adopted gripper revealed to be a key factor for succeeding in the competition. Finally, the EuRoC Floor Logistics and Manipulation challenge [6] assessed mobile manipulation capabilities both in simulation and remote robot control. From each of the aforementioned competitions, a large variety of diverse solutions at a hardware, software and algorithmic level originated [5, 7, 8]. These solutions are now becoming the starting point for teams participating in new editions of the competitions.

In the SciRoc competitions, we adopt a systematic evaluation approach with a scoring system similar to RoCKIn [2]. However, similarly to [5], in this episode we also introduce work orders coming from users (or customers) online, at execution time over a variety of objects with different sizes and that must preserve their quality. Moreover, the benchmarking approach, developed for EU project SoMa [9], is used as a reference to evaluate the performance of grasping.

Thus, SciRoc episode “Shopping Pick and Pack” challenge contributes in benchmarking mobile manipulation abilities of robots also focusing on a realistic business scenario.

3. Platforms allowed

Tasks must be completed using a fully autonomous robotic platform with mobile manipulation and perception capabilities (e.g., KUKA YouBot, Tiago, etc.). In particular, the robot must be able to navigate autonomously in the environment to reach the locations where products are placed. In addition, the robot must be able to detect, grasp and manipulate products in order to deliver them to the user (or customer). Moreover, the robot should be easily moved in and out the competition scenario, even when not in function, by maximum two team members with minimum effort.

The robot must have a noticeable **emergency stop button** that can be pressed at any time by any people involved in the episode (referees, users, team members, etc.) to shut off all motors in case of emergency. Teams must provide a document describing safety procedures and risk analysis for the use of their robot and any other equipment used during the challenge (see Section 12).

Robot inspection will be performed to test safety devices and procedures before the runs of the competition. No robot is allowed to participate in any test if safety procedures are not completed. Teams have to guarantee that safety devices and procedures are always working and enabled. Referees can check safety procedures at any time during the competition.

4. Scenario Setup

The episode takes place in an area reproducing a grocery shop. The shop is built with a shop window, a delivery area and shelves where products are located.

Customers will interact with the robot during the episode, as described in Section 6. Customers are chosen from the visitors of the competition after a clearance check, where they accept to take part to the episode.

Figure 1. Scenario layout.

The total area of the episode will be approximately eight by eight meters, as shown in Fig. 1. The scenario includes:

- A preparation area delimited with safety separators and a safety door that is reserved for the team that is about to start the next episode. Within this area any action on the robot is allowed and no score can be gained. As soon as a robot exits the preparation area, it cannot re-enter it. The robot has to autonomously exit the preparation area. The team has to clear this area as soon as possible, while the robot is performing the trial and the area can be occupied by the next team to start setup for the next run.
- A start/finish area (2 x 1.5 m) delimited with markers on the ground. In every test, the robot starts from this area.
- An order handout desk (1 x 1 m) with a tablet or screen for sending customer orders.
- Two shelving units (see example at the bottom of the document) labelled with a unique identification number. Among the available shelves, products will be set up at heights suitable for small-sized robots (e.g., YouBot) and for big-sized robots (e.g., Tiago). In the same shelf, products might be placed at different shelf levels.

- Robot delivery areas (desks 2 x 0.5 m each). Similar to shelves, for the two desks used as robot delivery areas, different heights will be set up for small and big sized robots.

Common furniture and packaged merchandise found at ordinary grocery shops will be used as the objects to be perceived and carried by the robots. The detailed description of all furniture, objects and products will be provided to the participating teams according to the schedule given in Section 6.2.

5. MK Data Hub Interaction

The Milton Keynes (MK) city - hosting the competition - is equipped with a data acquisition and management infrastructure (MK Data Hub) consisting of live sensors that reflect different aspects of the functionalities of the city (transport, environment, energy, water, etc.). The data gathered by the tablet and robots in this episode should be communicated to the infrastructure to contribute to the smart city digital platform.

In particular, referees inform the Data Hub about the number, shelf level and packaging size of the possible products to be requested by customers in their orders. The tablet collects the orders among the possible choices (see section 6), and communicates to the Data Hub the number and type of products requested by the customer. This information is provided by the hub to the robot upon robot's request, together with information regarding the location and availability of the requested products. While executing the task, the robot informs the hub with the number of products successfully collected for each type, missing products (if any) and instant of time at which the task is completed (i.e., products are packed).

Teams are notified according to the schedule specified in Section 6.2 by the organizers about the data and communication protocols that are required for interaction with the Data Hub.

6. Procedure

The episode will include one adult customer for each run who is randomly selected by the referees. The customer will send an order, that is not provided to teams before the run of the episode, and the robot has to figure out how to deliver the requested products one by one.

Order: the order will request the robot to deliver a number K of products that can have different type, packaging size and that can be located at different shelf levels. Shelf level and packaging size of the products will be decided by the referees and will be the same for all teams during the same trial. The number K of products is fixed for all teams during the same day. Each product is assigned a level of difficulty: easy, medium or hard. In particular, teams face the delivery task with increasing difficulty that will take place in different competition days:

- Qualification round 1 - the order requires two products of easy level of difficulty (K=2).
- Qualification round 2 - the order requires four products of easy and medium levels of difficulty (K=4).
- Final - six products of medium and hard levels of difficulty; including one duplicate and one new product from round 2 (K=6).

Delivered product: a product is considered as delivered only when it is placed in the delivery area without being in contact with any part of the robot, and the robot has announced its delivery.

Runs/trials: a single run or trial consists of P *steps* (a single phase repeating P times) executed sequentially without any interruptions and in any order, starting from the start area. Once it is left, the start area cannot be re-entered. During a single step, the robot can only deliver **one of the K products** requested in the order (i.e., they must be delivered one by one). A robot can automatically continue to the next step at any time if it is unable to execute or fully complete a step, provided this transition is announced. The robot must announce the start of a new step (pick of a new product) to allow the referee and the audience better understand the behaviour of the robot. Similarly, the robot must announce the delivery of each of the products as well as the end on the trial once entered in the finish area. When the robot announces the end of the trial from the finish area the products are delivered by the human operator to the customer. To stop the time, the robot must simultaneously be in the finish area and announce the end of the trial. Hence, if the robot does not announce the end of the trial, the time is not stopped even if the robot is located in the finish area.

6.1 Expected behaviour of the robot

Preparations and start of the trial

- The robot is positioned in the starting area.
- A referee uses the tablet to send an order collected at most 3 minutes before from a customer. The order is sent to the Data Hub at least 1 minute before the scheduled start.
- The trial begins at the scheduled time; the timer starts, with the employee waiting for the robot to deliver the products.
- The robot requests the order from the data hub, together with the shelf ID of each of the requested products.
- When ready, the robot leaves the start area. The start area must be left by the robot within the first 5 minutes from the episode start.

Single step

- The robot chooses a product from the order to deliver and announces it.
- The robot approaches the target shelf according to the announced product.
- The robot perceives and grasps the announced product.

- The robot delivers the product to the robot delivery area, leaving it there. The product is considered delivered according to the definition provided at the beginning of this section.
- The robot announces the delivery of the product.

Multiple steps and finish of the trial

- After the execution of a single step, a new step can be started or the robot can go to the finish area and announce the end of the trial.
- After the robot announces the end of the trial while being in the finish area, the products are delivered by the human operator.

6.2 Team information and schedule

Any information (e.g., shelving, product details, communication protocol for the hub, etc.) will be provided to the teams 4-5 weeks before the competition.

The scenario in which the episode will run will be available during the setup days. Any mapping procedure can be performed, no major changes will be applied during the competition.

7. Timing

The maximum allowed time for a single qualification trial is **20** minutes. The timer starts immediately after the customer order is sent. During this time slot the team may attempt only one run of the episode.

The run for each team will start strictly at the scheduled time in order to avoid time shifts. Teams that are not ready to start at the designated time will lose some time but will still be able to run their test until the end of the assigned time slot. If a robot cannot start the episode (i.e., leave the start area) within the first 5 minutes of the time slot, it will be asked to be moved away. Time stops either at expiration or when the robot moves to the finish area and announces that it has completed the trial. Note that time is an important factor in this episode, and faster solutions are considered better in case of ties in the number of achievements.

In any case, the start area must be cleared within the first 5 minutes of the slot assigned to each team. After the robot exits the start area, teams have to clear the area immediately removing any other equipment (laptops, power cords, etc.). Further on, the start area becomes a finish position.

8. Score

The score of the episode is determined as a sum of points defined in a set of achievements and penalisations, based on objective measures.

8.1 Achievements

- The robot announces the start of a new step.
- The robot grasps a product (independently of its type). (Repeatable)
- The robot delivers a correct product to the robot delivery area. (Repeatable)
- The order delivers all the K products.
- Data Hub updated correctly for the remaining products on shelves. (Repeatable)
- The robot reaches the finish area.

8.2 Penalising behaviours

- The robot hits any of the furniture and objects. (Repeatable)
- The robot drops an object. (Repeatable)
- The robot announces the completion of a step when the product is not yet fully delivered. (Repeatable)
- The robot announces the delivery of an item which is not in the order or which has been already delivered. (Repeatable)
- The robot enters the finish area but does not announce the end of the trial within one minute.

8.3 Disqualifying behaviours

The episode is immediately stopped and any score achieved will be cancelled.

- The robot hits a human.
- The robot hits and damages the furniture and/or objects.

8.5 Overall score

The competition is arranged in two stages: 1) Competition Days (qualification rounds), 2) Final. The top 3 teams in the ranking of the Competition Days qualify for the final to be held in the last day of the competition. The final ranking for assigning the first, second and third place will be determined by the performance in the Final. During the competition days, several runs will be available to each team (let this number be M). Notice that M is the number of slots available for each team, it may differ from the actual number of performances of each team, if teams are not ready to attend some runs. During the Final, only one run will be performed.

Aggregate score of the Competition days. The aggregate score for each team for the M episodes performed during the Competition days will be determined according to the score system of the European Robotics League as follows:

- select the best N trials of the team
- determine the median of the scores of the N trials selected.

Let n be the position of the median in the ordered list of team scores, i.e., $n = (N + 1) / 2$ (when N is odd), then N (and consequently n) are determined according to the number of episodes scheduled M, according to the following table

M	N	n
6-9	5	3
10-12	7	4
13-15	9	5

In case of tie score for the access to the Final, the policy for tie breaking is described below. If such policy does not break the tie, all teams with the same score will enter the Final.

Tie breaker: In the case in which two teams have the same score the cumulative execution time over all the runs of the teams will break ties.

In case of tie score again, the rank will be the same. If teams with the same score are in the border limit to access the Final, all such teams will enter the Final.

9. Detailed instructions for referees

The referees/organizers must prepare a schedule to ensure an equal access of the arena to the participating teams for the setup days. Also they must make sure that all products in the shop are provided to the teams during the setup days for training purposes. The referees must check the robots and approve their safety mechanism before the actual trials of the competition.

Once the arena has been built, and before allowing the teams to access the arena, the referees must mark the start and finish locations, products and other furniture to ensure they are placed back on their default locations for the trials.

A competition schedule for the competition trials must be prepared in advance.

Time slots of 30 minutes (20 minute trials + 10 minutes of preparation and team exchange) is expected for every qualification trial. Each team must be given an equal opportunity to perform multiple trials (minimum 3 to maximum 9 per day, based on the time availability and the number of participating teams).

A minimum number of 2 referees and 1 volunteer acting as customer are required for execution of the test. The customer will be selected from the audience and is required to

sign a consensus form given prior to the trial. The referees should try to initialize the scenario before the trial and assign roles to the customer to collect orders.

For every trial, the referees must prepare the scenario according to the description provided in the “Procedures” section by distributing products in the shelves according to the schema available in the digital hub. In particular, they must establish the shelf level and packaging size of the products to deliver, and they must collect an order of K products according to the difficulty level of the day. The difficulty of different trials should be comparable.

To begin a trial, one of the referees must be standing at the order handout desk. They have the responsibility of announcing the start and stop of the benchmark according to the schedule. Referees are also in charge of 1) delivering the customer order (collected at most 3 minutes before) at least 1 minute before the start of the trial through the tablet app, 2) keeping track of the time and 3) placing and removing the objects from the robot delivery area to the order handout desk. The second referee will always be in the human operator’s area, ensuring the safe operation of the robot at all times and scoring the achievements and penalties using the provided score sheets.

At the end of a trial the referees cross check the score with each other, record the execution time on the score sheet, and confirm the score with the team leader of the participating team.

10. Detailed instructions for teams

Teams need to show safety mechanisms of their robots and to demonstrate their use once before the competition begins. They also need to communicate to the organizers the required information for operating and stopping the robot.

During the competition, teams must prepare their robots outside the arena and can only enter the arena at the assigned times. They must follow the schedule of the trial and comply with the timings described in the “Timing” section. Once the referee signals the end of the trial, the participating team must immediately remove the robot from the arena to allow the next team to enter. In particular, the robot can start the episode (i.e., leave the start area) at any time, but the time of the episode is fixed in the schedule and does not depend on the robot actions. If the robot is not able to leave the start area within the first 5 minutes of the time slot available to the team, the team will have to give up the run and clear the start area immediately. The test finishes at the scheduled time (i.e., 15 minutes after the scheduled start). When the episode ends, team have to remove the robot from the arena within 2 minutes, exiting through the finish area.

Teams are kindly requested to log and store the robot’s Internal data for every trial and to provide it to the organizers after the end of trials. This data will not be used during the competition, but it is used to produce and publish datasets for the benefit of the robotics community. This data must be expressed in the reference frame of the test bed which will be

clearly marked on it. There are no restrictions about the framerate and data can be saved at the rate they are acquired or produced. Only data relevant to the episode is expected to be logged and can be in the format of *rosvbag*, in particular the following data is expected to be logged:

1. Images processed for object perception and the calibration info for the images.
2. Point clouds used to recognize an object.
3. 2D estimated robot poses and 2D trajectories planned by the robot.
4. Laser scans and odometry used for estimating the pose.
5. Static transforms among robot frames.
6. Arm trajectories planned by the robot.

11. Ethical issues

Customers involved in the episode will be selected by referees among adult customers in the MK shopping mall. These customers will be informed about the task under execution.

The customers will be invited to sign a consensus form where they declare to have been informed about the above-mentioned information and that they volunteer to participate in the episode.

12. Safety procedures

The only humans inside the scenario are the referees. A specific safety separator will be provided by the constructors of the scenario to separate the robot movement and manipulation area from the human operator area.

Teams are responsible to describe safety procedures of the robots used during the challenge. A document describing such procedures and risk analysis must be submitted at registration time and will be used by referee at any time to guarantee safety when using the robot and to instruct customers participating to the episode.

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Appendix A. Score sheet

Team: _____

Execution Time: _____

Trial number: _____

Achievements:

- The robot announces the start of a new step.
- The robot grasps a product (independently of its type). No. ____
- The robot delivers a correct product to the robot delivery area. No. ____
- The order delivers all the K products.
- Data Hub updated correctly for the remaining products on shelves. No. ____
- The robot reaches the finish area.

Penalizing behaviors:

- The robot hits any of the furniture and objects. No. ____
- The robot drops an object. No. ____
- The robot delivers a product which is not in the order. No. ____
- The robot does not announce the end of the trial while in the finish area.

Disqualifying behaviors:

- The robot hits a human.
- The robot damages objects and furniture

Notes:

Appendix B. Reference image for shelves

Episode 10

Through the door

Technical Committee

Giulio Fontana, Politecnico di Milano, Italy

Matteo Matteucci, Politecnico di Milano, Italy

Francesco Riccio, Sapienza University of Rome, Italy

Gianluca Bardaro, The Open University, UK

External expert: Victor López, PAL Robotics, Spain

1. General Description

Episode 10 aims at evaluating the capability of a robot to interact with one of the most ubiquitous devices found in environments designed for humans: the **hinged door**.

A hinged door (often simply called “door” in the following) is an especially challenging device for robots. This is due to the fact that it has a very long history¹ of development over which the only design constraints were cost and fitness for human usage. As a consequence, a door is one of the pieces of human engineering that are most closely matched to human capabilities and limitations. Due to this perfect match, a door is as easy and natural to use for standard humans as it is awkward or impossible for “non-standard” actors. These include -for instance- small children, people on wheelchairs, animals and mobile machines. In the context of this document we are going to focus on one specific kind of mobile machine: the **autonomous robot**.

In environments that can be subject to modifications to make them more machine-friendly (such as factories), hinged doors are usually banned and substituted with more suitable devices, e.g. automated sliding doors. However, approach taken by research on autonomous robots is usually the opposite, i.e. it is the robot which has to adapt -thanks to its physical and/or cognitive capabilities- to unmodified human environments. Given the previous considerations, this puts “operating a hinged door” very high on a hypothetical shortlist of capabilities that any robot must possess in order to successfully operate in common human environments.

(Starring)
SUSAN BRACKEN • LARRY O'DWYER • GENE ROSS

¹ The history of the hinged door is indeed extraordinarily long. Devices similar to those used today date back to the Roman Empire, while stone-hinged doors were in use in ancient Egypt more than 3500 years ago. A consequence of this is that doors are extraordinarily present -with different roles- in human folklore and culture, as exemplified by the (slightly edited) image above.

1.1 Definition of “door”

We humans are so used to doors, and their features are so standardised, that it seems strange to write them down in a systematic way. However, for the sake of a clear and unambiguous definition of the type of problem represented by Episode 10, it is useful to define a (hinged) door as a device with the following features:

- the door has the shape of a vertical and flat *panel* surrounded by a *frame*;
- the panel can be transparent to light, opaque or light-diffusive, or be a combination of areas with different light-transmitting properties;
- panel dimensions are suitable for easy traversal by a standard human (for indoor applications, typical dimensions are 70-90 cm of width by 210 cm of height);
- there may be *subpanels* enclosed in the door panel, i.e. areas of the door panel having different visual properties (colour, light transmission, texture, ...) from the rest of the panel;
- the door's only possibility of movement is rotation around a vertical axis located in close proximity (i.e., within a few centimetres) from one of the vertical edges of the panel: the physical mechanism supporting the rotation is usually composed of two or more *hinges*;
- the hinges are the only points of contact between the door panel and the rest of the environment, and connect the panel to the frame;
- the door is intended to be incorporated into a wall or other partition separating two environments: the door is *closed* when coplanar with such partition, and *open* when in any other position;
- usually angular movement (around the rotation axis) is only allowed in one of the two possible directions: i.e., the door panel can move into one of the two environments separated by the partitioning wall, but not into the other;
- the range of angular positions that the door can take spans from 0° (corresponding to the *closed* position) to at 90° or more;
- the hinges support the weight of the door panel so that -whatever its angular position- its lower edge is in close proximity to the floor but does not touch it;
- the frame surrounds the door panel along its vertical edges and usually also along its upper edge, but not along the lower edge (i.e., the one in proximity to the floor);
- the door has a locking mechanism that, when the door is closed, has to be disengaged before the door can be moved;
- the door is manipulated by through the handling of a *handle*, which can take a wide variety of shapes but is always designed to be easily gripped by humans;
- handles are usually fitted on both sides of the door panel, in order to let users operate it from both environments separated by the door;
- the handle is located on the door panel in the vicinity of the vertical edge of the door that is farther from the rotation axis: this has the consequence of transforming modest forces perpendicular to the door panel applied to the handle into a significant torque around the rotation axis;
- the height of the handles from the ground is such that a standing adult human of standard height can easily manipulate them;

- the locking mechanism is usually linked to the handle, in the sense that the handle must be moved (rotated, depressed, ...) in order to unlock the door;
- the locking mechanism is usually designed in such a way that to lock the door it is usually sufficient to push it to its *closed* position;
- unlocking the door can require the application of significant forces to the handle, while moving the door once unlocked requires, in optimal conditions, the application of very small forces.

Section 4 of this document provides information about the setup used to implement a hinged door in the context of Episode 10.

It must be noted that the features above describe doors that do not have any mechanisms influencing the dynamic behaviour of the door panel. Such mechanisms are indeed common, and include both intentional and unintentional ones.

Among intentional alterations to door behaviour we can cite:

- elastic forces opposing panel rotation;
- automatic (elastic or motorised) return to the closed position;
- viscous damping of panel rotation.

Unintentional alterations to door behaviour are usually due to faults and/or obstructions, and include:

- friction, either constant or dependent on angular position;
- limitations of the angular range;
- torque opposing door motion, either constant or dependent on the angular position of the panel (e.g., effect of wind);
- effect of other users operating the door from the other side;
- ...

In many real-world situations more than one among the above cited alterations can affect the same door, thus leading to a wide range of altered door behaviours with respect to the baseline.

Episode 10, for the time being at least, focuses on baseline door behaviour.

The authors of this document are well aware that most of the above alterations to door behaviour can be simulated by introducing suitable actuation and control actions, and have already devised the technical means through which such alterations can be introduced. For this reason, the door assembly described in Section 4 is designed to support the installation of additional components aimed at this goal.

2. Main scientific challenge

Dexterous motions and gestures are of key interest to address countless applications where the robot has to act on the environment. This is especially relevant for humanoid robots that are designed to surrogate -- and eventually substitute -- human motions, and to properly behave in a human-friendly world. In fact, human environments, and its components, are designed to accommodate our body strengths and limitations. For example let us consider the shape of keyboards, chairs, windows, doors and handles. Operating in such environments without the capability to interact with those components is extremely difficult, and prevents agents to be effective and independent.

Robots are no exception, and to allow them to freely operate in our world, we need to provide them with the ability to smoothly interact with all the environmental components, and to replicate human motions. This is an extremely challenging task that has become to be regarded as fundamental to truly enable autonomy on robots.

In this episode, we focus on one of these robot-environment interactions to improve local robot behaviour in addressing doors [Meeussen et al., 2010;Rühr et al., 2012;Gu et al., 2017]. In particular, this episode is designed to provide a common testbed and a baseline for generating effective behaviours for robots acting in typical human-populated environments.

Since doors are a constant and dynamic component of our scenarios, being capable of mastering doors is key to develop autonomy in robots. Moreover, not being able to cope with them can be harmful as it might prevent the robot to complete its jobs (e.g. delivery).

The community has already shown a great interest in tackling such a problem. Given the existing literature, the task of opening a door can be divided in four distinct phases: detection, approach, manipulation and traversal. Hence, related works can be classified in accordance to their contribution to these phases. For example, several approaches have been proposed to door detection. Image-based methods have been proven to be capable to detect different doors in various scenarios [Borgsen et al., 2014;Goron et al., 2012], though this class of solution is often affected by false positives [Sekkal et al., 2013].

Conversely, [Quintana et al., 2016] proposes a model-based method for detecting doors in cluttered environments using rgb-d sensor information. [Chen et al, 2014] describe their solution based on a deep model learned through a convolutional network. It is important to say that, as highlighted by these contributions, the challenge of this phase of the task is to develop a system able to recognize doors (1) in different states (closed, open and semi-open) [Quintana et al., 2016] and (2) with different environmental conditions (cluttering, occlusions, lightning) [Chen et al, 2014], as well as (3) to estimate the orientation of the door [Klingbeil et al., 2010].

The approach phase is key to have an exploitable positioning of the robot with respect to the door. Such a task is usually considered as a navigation and positioning task, which is not strictly depending on the object to approach [Kriegel et al., 2011;Koyuncu et al., 2010]. However, we can summarize the key aspects that might affect a successful robot positioning in the object-target appearance, and the robot embodiment [Gomez et al., 2013].

The manipulation phase is key to this episode and usually requires the robot to: detect the type of handle, trigger the related behaviour, and perform the desired movement [Li et al., 2015]. This is a crucial phase of the task that requires visual monitoring and manipulation, simultaneously. For example, [Rusu et al., 2009;Klingbeil et al., 2010] exploit 3D laser scan to detect the type of handle and determine robot motions. [Meeussen et al., 2010] improve handle detection by considering both geometry and appearance. Then, upon detection, the authors use a compliant and force controlled task formalism (TFF - Task Frame Formalism) to plan for robot motions. Similarly, [Rühr et al., 2012] propose a general framework to open doors and drawers. They also rely on geometry and appearance of the handle, but they improve robot manipulation skill by exploiting impedance control and learning the kinematic model of the objects. It is worth highlighting that the authors store learned handle models to improve future interactions and motions executions. Differently, [Gu et al., 2017] exploit deep

learning to develop an end-to-end system that collects images and generate desired motions by relying upon off-policy training of deep Q-functions. The author reduce training time by running several parallel simulations of the robot. Numerous approaches address the problem of locating and manipulating doors handles, however a key challenge remains that of generating a flexible approach able to generalize to different types of handles and doors (e.g. sliding doors).

The last phase of the task is to traverse the door, which can be considered as a navigation task once the door is open. Few works start the maneuver while opening the door [Jain et al., 2008]. For example, [Chitta et al., 2010] generate a cost map depending on the current position of the door and then run an Anytime Repairing A* (ARA*) to determine the best motion for the robot base. [Srinivasa et al., 2010] introduce HERB, a complete system able to manipulate and traverse a door simultaneously. The authors developed the Constrained BiDirectional Rapidly-exploring Random Tree (CBiRRT) to generate effective robot motions. The key challenge of this phase is to provide the robot with the ability to plan several steps ahead of both base motions and handle manipulation actions.

The aforementioned contributions highlight how door negotiation is widely perceived as a fundamental skill for achieving autonomy through the robotics community, a fact confirmed by the role given to it in robotic competitions as the DARPA challenge². In this competition, the robots had to approach a closed (hinged) door, open it and walk through it. The task was considered complete when all points of robot ground contact were past the door threshold³. In this context, the IHMC team [Johnson et al., 2015] exploited a combination of two methods to locate handles (and doors). The first a coloring technique to adapt the color in a point cloud and the second a texturing method to adapt the color of the real object to the point cloud. The robot then manipulates the handle by exploiting the concept of interactable object as introduced by the authors. In [Banerjee et al., 2015] the WPI-CMU team exploited a mix of 2D and 3D geometric segmentation techniques to detect the door and approach it. Then, the robot uses a modified TrajOpt algorithm to generate effective trajectories while maintaining a reduced computation time. [Zucker et al., 2015] describe the DARPA challenge of the DRC-HUBO robot. They also detect the door handle through geometrical features and plan for robot motions by exploiting key poses to interpolate the task.

Despite the remarkable contributions and effort done to address and complete this challenge, proposed solutions still do not satisfy the expected level of dexterity nor achieve the desired natural and robust behaviour. This suggests the difficulty of mastering such a task for an autonomous robot, and the need to tackle such a challenge. In the SciRoc project we propose the Door episode to contribute in this direction.

We come finally to Episode 10, whose goal is to define a standardised way to test the capabilities of autonomous robots to solve the door-related problems described in this section. In doing so, Episode 10 leverages the methodological framework developed by former research projects RoCKIn and RockEU2 [Amigoni et al., 2015]. In fact the ambitions

² A quick recapitulation of the tasks that the robots participating to the last DARPA challenge were required to perform is available in video form here: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=YQvEy3qTm8c>

³ Defining a criterium to decide if a robot has gone through a door is indeed a key problem. The approach of Episode 10 is described in Section 6 of this document.

of Episode 10 go beyond a simple “door test” and aim, instead, at a scientifically grounded “door benchmark”.

3. Platforms allowed

This episode is open to any robot capable of executing the actions described in Section 6, (possibly with human help when allowed). In particular, being able to manipulate the door handle is not necessary to complete Episode 10, though it is necessary to get a full score (see Section 8 for details).

The robot should be easily moved in and out the competition scenario, even if completely unresponsive, by maximum two team members with minimum effort.

The robot must be provided with a clearly visible and easily accessible **emergency button** that can be pressed at any time by anyone involved in the episode (referees, team members, etc.). Upon pressing the emergency button, the robot should immediately stop executing any motion with any moving parts.

Teams must provide a document describing safety procedures and risk analysis for the use of their robot and any other equipment used during the challenge (see Section 12).

IMPORTANT General rule: Robot inspection will be performed to test safety devices and procedures before the runs of the competition. No robot is allowed to participate in any test if safety procedures are not completed. Teams have to guarantee that safety devices and procedures are always working and enabled. Referees can check safety procedures at any time during the competition.

4. Scenario Setup

The scenario setup is composed of a **door assembly** comprising the door that the robot has to operate, and a surrounding **test area** where the robot can move. Additional information about the setup concern the materials used to build the door assembly and the methods to affix the door assembly to the floor of the test area, so that it will not be moved if the robot hits its elements or applies anomalous forces to the door. All of these elements are defined in the following parts of this section.

A simulator for the scenario of Episode 10 is available at

<https://sites.google.com/view/e10-open-the-door/home>

4.1 Door assembly

Being Episode 10 focused on door operation by robots, the key element of the scenario setup is -quite naturally- a door. While all locations where Episode 10 takes place can be reasonably be expected to include doors, it is not possible to expect that such doors are both suitable for Episode 10 and sufficiently similar from one location to the other. For this reason, a *door assembly* provided by SciRoc is used for the Episode.

The door assembly must fulfil requirements that are partly conflicting. Among these:

- it is necessary that the door is fully realistic, but also sufficiently robust not to be damaged by the robots;

- it is preferable that the door cover can be easily exchanged -in order to test how robots behave with different types;
- it must be sufficiently stable to withstand being hit by a robot without collapsing, and at the same time it must be as small and light as possible for easy transportation and storage;
- it should be built in such a way that additional devices can be easily added to the assembly (e.g., laboratory equipment) while maintaining a standard-door look;
- it should be compatible with both a stand-alone, self-supported installation and with being mounted as part (or at one extremity of) existing walls and partitions;
- if installed in a stand-alone way it should include wall-like surfaces on the sides of the door in order to simulate a realistic setting, while such surfaces should be absent for in-wall installations.

A final requirement, introduced to enable future developments of the benchmark, is the capability to install additional actuation and control devices in order to introduce controlled alterations to the dynamic behaviour of the door; without, of course, compromising the fact that the door assembly should look and operate as similarly as possible to a standard hinged door. For this reason, means to electrically control the movement of the door panel have been introduced in the design. Transmission of momentum from a -suitably controlled- electrical motor to the door and back is obtained via a belt-and-gear assembly. In particular, the motor connects to the door by means of a gear with the same rotation axis of the door hinges, mechanically affixed to the door panel. In order to reach the desired precision of control, this gear is quite large and thus protrudes slightly from the “wall” surrounding the door; other than that, the elements of the control system are supposed to be hidden from view (enclosed within the “wall” and/or mounted on the side of the door that is not initially visible to the robot).

The resulting door assembly, which complies with all of the conflicting constraints listed at the beginning of this section, is illustrated by the following figures⁴.

⁴ The figures are screenshots from the Sketchup software used to design the door assembly. Sketchup files are available on request.

[Left] The complete assembly in stand-alone installation similar to a standard-sized door installed in a portion of wall (grey bricks). In the figure, the door panel is brown; the grey element is the handle. The bars at the sides, which are hidden in this representation, prevent the assembly from collapsing in case it is hit by a robot.

While the door assembly appears to be a standard door, it is actually a special-purpose device. The surfaces of the door panel and of the wall surrounding the door are thin (1 cm) *cover panels* affixed to a sturdy metal frame. The panes are made of MDF (or other suitable material) and can be easily painted or otherwise decorated, thus enabling a wide range of appearance options without compromising the stability of the assembly. They can be quickly removed for maintenance, or exchanged with differently finished alternatives whenever required.

[Right] The frame of the door assembly without the cover panels for the wall elements, showing the frame of the assembly. The small rectangular cutout on the right of the handle is designed to accommodate the (fully standard) mechanical element that is engaged by the lock mechanism when the door is closed.

The following figure (below) shows the door assembly without any cover panels. It is now apparent how a cutout similar to the one described above is incorporated in the frame of the door panel as well. This is used for installation of a (fully standard) handle and lock mechanism. Please note that mounting the elements of the locking mechanisms this way (i.e., on supporting structures that insert into the cutouts of the frame) allows for swapping these elements with reasonable ease without need to dismantle the whole assembly. Other features of the door assembly frame are described below.

[Left] As shown in the figures, the door panel is supported by 3 Ball-Bearing Hinges (might be 4 in the final build). In this way the door assembly is able to withstand much larger mechanical forces without damage when compared with a standard door. The frame of the door assembly is built of 40mm x 40mm modular aluminium profiles (see Section 4.3), suitably connected. Some reinforcement elements (e.g., L-shaped 5mm thick aluminium panels or angle brackets) will be used on the connections between the vertical and horizontal elements of the frame to strengthen such joints and to ensure their geometry. Both aspects are important in view of the key role of these joints in supporting the door panel and door actuation devices (e.g., the gear on top of the door).

[Right] This image shows the stationary parts of the frame. It shows, in particular, how the swinging frame which simulates the door is connected to the stationary support frame by heavy-duty hinges (Ball-Bearing Hinges). This makes the assembly much stronger than possible with the (usually weak) hinges used by conventional doors, without compromising the realism of the door movement. It is important to note that the hinges should have low friction, but not so low as to allow the door to move more than 30°-45° if pushed gently. Too low friction makes controlling the door movement more difficult for the robot, and lets the robot perform some actions (e.g., closing the door) simply by shoving to the door panel, which is not a sufficiently precise method and thus should not be encouraged. For this reason, hinges used for the door assembly should preferably offer some means of adjusting friction: for instance, friction can be simulated by the action of the motor connected to the gear. The stationary frame is composed of 40 mm x 40 mm modular aluminium profiles (see Section 4.2) for its main elements.

The next figure provides a closer view of the swinging frame of the door panel.

This image highlights the presence of a gear on top of the door. This is designed to let the door panel be mechanically controlled by door-actuation devices without need for these to be attached to the door panels. In this way, actuating the door panel does not introduce any constraints to the possibility of exchanging the panels.

Finally, the image below illustrates some details. In particular it shows:

- (in pink) a front view of the box supporting the plate engaged by the locking mechanism when the door is closed and locked;
- (in blue) thin panel elements used to occlude the air gaps at the sides of the door;

Finally, here is the view of both the stationary frame and the door swinging frame with the supporting elements used to strengthen it.

4.2 Dimensions and test area

The door assembly is 180cm wide and 230cm high. Depth is mostly due to the thickness of the aluminium frames, 40mm, and the thickness of the panels used to cover the frame. Since the door will be installed in a simulated wall provided at the event the overall thickness will be probably dominated by the wall.

In order to ease installation of the door assembly at the premises where the benchmark takes place, an **external frame** will be sent there to be installed before the actual door assembly arrives. Once the external frame is incorporated into an existing structure, installing the door assembly only requires to bolt the door assembly described by Section 4.1 onto it.

Below is a picture of the external frame, which is built out of the same 40mm x 40mm aluminium profile as the door assembly frame.

Dimensions are slightly larger than the door assembly, in order to easily accommodate it inside. An additional 40mm of clearance has been introduced in order to have some space (if needed) for adjustments. It must be noted how inclusion of the external frame into an existing structure also removes the necessity to affix the door assembly to the floor (see Section 4.4).

The swinging panel of the door assembly is designed to simulate the standard panel of commercial 90 cm by 210 cm (H) doors⁵ (see also “A note on door panels” below). The door passage of the door assembly (i.e., the portion of the plane of the door that is available for passage when the door is open at 90°) is also 90 cm wide by 210 cm high. There is an additional 15mm above the door where the gear is and a 5mm gap on the bottom of the door to make sure it has enough space to rotate without touching the floor.

The test area for Episode 10 is the area where the door assembly is located, comprising also the operating areas for the robot on both sides of the door. Its preferred shape and dimensions are those of a rectangle of 10 x 5 m, where the projection on the floor of the door panel (door closed) lies on the major axis of the test area and is perpendicular to it. In the preferred setup, the plane of the door is at a distance of 7m from one of the short sides of the test area, and the start pose of the robot (as exemplified blue circle in the picture, see

⁵ Please note that, given the way the door assembly is built, it would not be easy -should the necessity arise- to modify the structure in order to accommodate a different door width.

Section 6) lies within the larger of the two areas that the plane of the door divides the test area into, i.e. in the 7 m x 5 m portion that is on the left in the figure.

As already specified above, these features of the test area are *preferred* but not mandatory. Shape, dimensions and positioning of the test area, as well as location of the door assembly within it, can be subjected to change in order to adapt the testbed to the available space where it is installed.

The only mandatory constraints on the test area are those needed for the feasibility of the benchmark procedure described in Section 6 of this document, i.e.:

1. every robot executing the benchmark must be given sufficient space to comfortably manoeuvre on both sides of the door;
2. the door panel must be visible from the starting position of the robot (possibly requiring only a rotation of the robot on the spot to reach visibility, but no translation).

A note on door panels

Door dimensions are standardised. 90 cm of width, i.e., the dimension chosen for Episode 10, is the maximum among the common options. However, it must be noted that a 90 cm *door* does not have a 90 cm *door panel*: standards specify the dimension of the passage, not of the panel. Door panels are slightly wider than the passage, as they are designed to rest against the borders of the door frame when closed: this makes the door not bi-directional (differently from panel of the door assembly of Episode 10), as it lets the door only open in one direction.

The arrangement where the door goes against the frame when closed is useful to limit the passage of air around the door. In order to further limit such passage, standard doors also have “lips” protruding from both long sides (i.e. the one with the hinges and the opposite one) that superpose with elements of the frame. Such “lips” also contribute to increase the overall width of the door panel with respect to the width of the door passage.

In the end, dimensions for a standard 90 cm door are:

- width of passage: 90 cm
- height of passage: 210 cm
- width of door panel, including lips: 93 cm
- width of door panel, without lips: 91.5 cm

For Episode 10, it was chosen to simulate a 90 x 210 cm door with no “lips”.

4.3 Materials

For what concerns the door assembly, its structural elements are realised using modular profile elements for easy construction⁶. This way, not only assembling and modifying the assembly is easier, but also -and most importantly- additional elements can be fitted to the frame as required in a secure and quick way to suit the requirements of each installment of Episode 10, without any need to modify the structure in any way. Such modular systems, in fact, include mechanisms (such as slots and special nuts to be inserted into the slots) to easily mount and dismount additional objects.

Another reason to choose modular elements for the frame of the door assembly is to make the exchange of assembly elements (such as cover panels or handle and lock mechanisms) as quick and easy as possible, thus making it possible to switch the door panel between one execution of Episode 10 and the next during the same installment: for instance to ensure that the robots under test are capable of successfully operate a range of different types of door.

4.4 Contact with the floor

There are no elements of the door frame in contact with the floor since it will be encased in the wall and it is lifted 5mm above the floor. Horizontality is important to ensure that the motion of the door panel is not influenced by gravity, as only if the rotation axis is perfectly vertical gravity does not exert any torque on the panel.

In order to avoid the possibility of the door assembly being moved accidentally by the robots executing Episode 10, it was decided to create an external frame to which the door assembly is attached. This external frame gets encased into a surrounding wall or other structural element. The best way to do this depends on the type of floor, wall and the venue where the Episode takes place. The choice of the best method is left to the technicians responsible for the setup of the infrastructure for Episode 10 in the specific setting of each installment.

⁶ Many suppliers exist of such elements, the one chosen for the realization of the structure is: <https://www.item24.com/>

The used products are:

<https://product.item24.it/en/productdetails/products/construction-profiles-8-1001042794/profile-8-40x40-light-natural-2633/>

<https://product.item24.it/en/productdetails/products/angle-bracket-zn-1001046547/angle-bracket-set-8-80x80-41132/>

<https://product.item24.it/en/productdetails/products/standard-fastening-sets-1001012015/standard-fastening-set-8-bright-zinc-plated-2607/>

<https://product.item24.it/en/productdetails/products/ball-bearing-hinge-1001042820/ball-bearing-hinge-8-40x40-49411/>

The easiest way to anchor the door assembly to the floor is to drill holes in the floor and use L-shaped brackets affixed to the side of the door assembly to connect them to screws engaging suitable anchors set in the floor holes; however, this method damages the floor.

A final issue related to contact with the floor concerns how to compensate for an irregular and/or non-horizontal floor. In fact the wall element incorporating the door assembly is a large object, and over relevant distances (3m for the larger dimension) it is not reasonable to expect that floors, including indoor high-quality ones, are perfectly planar. Therefore, it is suggested that suitable elastic elements (e.g., neoprene mats) are interposed between the elements of the door assembly resting on the floor and the floor itself. In case of severe irregularities, adjustable feet⁷ are advisable. If these are used, in order to maintain the distance between the door and the floor it will be necessary to move down the attachment points of the hinges along the vertical beam of the stationary frame⁸.

5. MK Data Hub Interaction

No direct interaction between the Episode and the Digital Hub is foreseen. No interaction occurs, either, between the Episode and the SciRoc app.

6. Procedure

The procedure that a robot must follow to execute the benchmark of Episode 10 is described below. In the description we will make reference to the elements of the door as defined in Section 1.1.

Please note that in this section action descriptions are focused on their execution; the criteria used to determine -for scoring purposes- if an action has been successfully executed are described in Section 8.

The door used for Episode 10 is always in the *closed* position at the start of the benchmark. The closed door is also locked by its standard locking mechanism. The robot system subjected to the benchmark of Episode 10 is required to perform, in order, the following actions:

1. **Reach or be brought to the start pose.**

[This is a preparatory step that does not contribute to the scoring. For this reason, it is acceptable if the robot is positioned in the start pose by human team members.]

The position of the start pose is chosen by the referees, in the previous pictures it is represented by the blue circle on the ground. Its maximum distance from the door is 8m from the door (calculated on a horizontal plane, from the door handle). The orientation of the start pose does not necessarily put the door in view of the robot;

⁷ The following is an example of one of the simplest types:

<https://product.item24.it/en/productdetails/products/knuckle-feet-1001042859/knuckle-foot-d40-m10x80-black-26574/>

⁸ Please note that lowering the door along the stationary frame to compensate for feet height will, of course, increase the vertical distance between the upper horizontal element of the swinging frame supporting the door panel and the horizontal element of the stationary frame. If the two are expected to be joined by some sort of measuring and/or actuation device, this will need to be taken into consideration while designing the mounting arrangement of such device.

however, the door panel will be fully visible to the robot from the start pose.

Episode 10's door can will be incorporated into a wall or other partition. More than one door can be present in the environment where the Episode takes place: in such a case the robot should select the door that is closer to the start pose.

2. Approach the door.

At least one point of the robot must arrive within 1 m from the handle located on the *starting side* of the door assembly. The starting side of the door assembly is the side visible from the start pose⁹.

3. Touch the door handle.

There are no limitations concerning what part of the robot touches the handle, provided that a physical contact occurs.

4. Unlock the door.

Unlocking the door means "prepare it so that it can be subsequently opened by applying only a pushing or pulling force". For most types of locking mechanism the process of opening the door must be initiated during the unlocking in order to be successful. In these cases, action "unlock the door" comprises also action "initiate opening", as the robot will need to execute both actions in a coordinated way. The two types of handles are the lever one and the knob one (see section 6.2).

It is faculty of the robot's team to request that a referee executes action "Unlock the door" instead of having it executed by the robot. The team can take this decision before the execution of the Episode or during its execution: in both cases, the referee waits for the robot to have completed the "Touch the handle" action before proceeding to unlock the door.

When referee intervention has been requested, as soon as the referee touches the door or the handle the unlocking action is considered irreversibly as executed by the referee, independently from the actions of the robot and their effects.

If the door lock requires initiation of door opening concurrently with the unlocking, the referee will also perform such initiation, leaving the door in a state that: (i) is stationary and (ii) is as close to the closed state as allowed by the physical characteristics of the locking mechanism and the need to leave the door unlocked. If the robot accidentally locks the door again after it has been unlocked by a referee, the referee will repeat the unlocking action. This can occur any number of times but leads to penalisation (see Section 8).

IMPORTANT: the referee will proceed to unlock the door only if they feel that the procedure is completely safe. No actions requiring proximity between robot and referee will be executed if the robot is behaving in a way that is deemed as "possibly dangerous" by the referee. In order to promote safety, whenever possible the referee will try to unlock the door from the other side.

5. Pass through the door.

The robot needs to open the (now unlocked) door sufficiently for the robot to go through it, and to actually navigate through the opening to reach the other side. The opening of the door can be executed with any technique (excluding those that can

⁹ The starting side defines a half-space, whose only boundary is a plane. Such plane is the one parallel to the door panel (when close) that has equal distances to the two faces of the standard door panel incorporated into the door assembly. The point where such distances are measured is at handle height vertically, and horizontally on the median vertical axis of the standard door panel.

damage the door), e.g. by manipulating the handle or the door panel with a hand effector, by pushing the panel using the robot base, by using a special-purpose tool, etc.

6. **Close the door.**

The door must be moved towards its closed position until its locking mechanism touches the corresponding plate on the door frame.

7. **Lock the door.**

The locking mechanism must be brought back to the “locked” state that it had at the start of the benchmark. This action can be executed with any technique (excluding those that can damage the door), e.g. by manipulating the handle or the door panel, or by pushing the panel using the robot base. Most standard door locks engage automatically if the door panel is pushed or pulled to its closed position; other types require manipulation of the handle.

During the execution of the benchmark, nobody except referees is allowed to be closer to the robot than 5 m.

Note: special exceptions to this rule can be made by referees in case the robot executing the benchmark is a biped needing a supporting crane pushed by a human. In these cases, special instructions are given by referees to the team members (usually one) operating the crane: a typical example is the prohibition to touch the robot or the door assembly. Failure to comply with the special instructions counts as a *disqualifying behaviour* (see Section 8).

6.1 Falls and manual get-up

Some types of robots -notably, bipeds- are dynamically stable, and thus subject to the risk of falling to the floor.

If a robot falls to the floor during a run of Episode 10, the benchmark is considered as ended at the moment of the fall. The only exceptions are the following:

1. the robot gets up on its own **within 2 minutes**;
2. the robot's team requests a **manual get-up**, provided that this is the first such request during the run.

A manual get-up is the possibility for the team to intervene and bring back the robot to its operational position manually. During a manual get-up, the only action allowed to team members is physically hauling the robot from the ground and setting it down again on the floor in the same pose it was in before falling.

A team can make a maximum of one request for manual get-up per benchmark run. The request must be addressed to the referees. Team members cannot enter the test area until the request has been explicitly accepted, and must leave the area as soon as the robot is again in its operational position.

After the execution of the manual get-up, the referees check that the pose of the robot is the same it had immediately before the fall. Referees can request that the team changes the robot's pose as many times as needed to meet this requirement. Once the referee declares that the requirement is met, the robot can proceed with the execution of the benchmark.

Requesting a manual get-up counts as a penalising behaviour for the robot and thus influences its score: see Section 8 for details.

The manual get-up does not reset the timer and the benchmark has to be completed within the original time-slot.

6.2 Variable elements of the door assembly

The procedure described above is fixed, but the physical setup of the door assembly used for its execution is subject to variations: not only among different installments of Episode 10, but also *during the course of a single installment*. These have the objective of making the features of the benchmark not completely known to teams (or at least not known well in advance of the execution of the benchmark). Variations are used to differentiate the features of different executions of the benchmark, while leaving both the procedure of the benchmark and its broad level of difficulty unmodified. The organisers of the Episode can execute variations at any time and with any frequency, the only constraint being their compatibility with the schedule of the Episode and of the whole SciRoc Challenge, and the need to avoid disruptions to the work of teams.

Variations in the door assembly correspond to exchanging one or more of its **variable elements** (see below) for alternative ones. Such variations can occur at any time during the competition, and especially from one day to the next¹⁰.

Variable elements that can be exchanged are:

1. the door cover panel;
2. the handle;
3. the unlocking mechanism;
4. the opening direction.

For what concerns the door cover panel (i.e. the panel mounted on the door assembly that simulates the look of a standard door), it is selected among a set of cover panels sharing the same dimensions (90 cm x 210 cm) but having different features. Differences among the panels might include, but are not limited to: type of surface (flat or shaped), colour, presence and type of subpanels. In general, any commonly available type of commercial door panel can be used (in emulated form) for Episode 10.

For the handle, similar considerations apply. Thus, the set of handles that the robot may find installed on the door panel during the execution of Episode 10 includes any commonly available type of commercial door handle: there are two types of handles that a robot might find while approaching the door and trying to unlock it. The first one is the most common one found in most doors and the one represented in the pictures used in this rulebook: the lever handle. In this case it is required to apply some force on the lever, towards the ground, in order to unlock the door. Next is the knob handle, this is a more complex operation for a robot since it is required to rotate the knob counterclockwise in order to unlock the door.

Possible unlocking mechanisms are of two types:

- those requiring that the handle is turned *and* (at the same time) pushed or pulled¹¹;
- those only requiring that the door is pushed or pulled, with or without need to overcome a small initial mechanical resistance.

¹⁰ The door assembly is designed to ease these exchanges, that take place in a few minutes.

¹¹ The fact that pushing or pulling is required depends on the opening direction of the door.

The robot needs to inspect the door and/or try it in order to ascertain what kind of unlocking mechanism is installed.

During the team preparation days of the competition and during the competition itself, samples of all the cover panels, all the door handles and all locking mechanisms that may be used for the current installment of Episode 10 are available to teams for inspection at the competition venue. In this context, “inspection” means “*any activity (including measurement or scanning) that does not require to manipulate the inspected item or move it from its location*”.

IMPORTANT Teams are required to allow other teams the same access to the samples that they are getting. Referees have the faculty of inflicting score penalisations or -in the worst cases- disqualification from the Episode to teams “hogging” the samples.

Finally, for the opening direction of the door there are three possibilities:

- inwards (i.e., the robot should pull the door panel to open the door);
- outwards (i.e., the robot should push the door panel to open it);
- both (i.e. the robot can choose among pulling and pushing since both allow to open the door).

While the hinges of the door assembly allow both opening directions, a mechanical detent can be used to limit door opening to one only of the two directions or the electrical motor connected to the door will limit one direction. The detent would be built in such a way that it is impossible for the robot to detect its state, so the robot needs to try and move the door to find out its direction of movement.

Knowing beforehand the direction of movement of the door is a big help for the robot. For this reason, such direction should be changed often and without letting team members know it.

7. Timing

For each team the start of the benchmark is determined in accordance with the schedule of Episode 10. Each scheduled execution of Episode 10 by a robot is called a **run** of the benchmark. The final score achieved by the robot X depends on its performance over multiple runs of the benchmark, according to the scoring mechanism described in Section 8.

Scheduled times for the runs of a given team are published by the referees well in advance of the runs. **Such times are not flexible**. In particular, the *scheduled end time* for each run is rigidly enforced¹² and is not influenced by the fact that the robot is or is not ready at the scheduled start time. These times are defined as follows:

- **Scheduled start time** is defined as the time chosen by the referees for the beginning of the run;

¹² This rigidity is necessary to preserve the timing of the SciRoc Challenge, in order to make it more attractive to the public. Unexpected pauses and delays have, in fact, a heavily disruptive effect on an event such as the Challenge and must be avoided. Also, rigidity in timing ensures that the scoring takes into consideration the capability of a team to get the robot ready for a benchmark in a reliable and repeatable way.

- **Scheduled end time** is defined as *scheduled start time + timeout* (timeout is defined in Section 7.1).

In case of delays due to the organisation, the scheduled start time is moved forward accordingly in order not to penalise the team.

The start of a run occurs at the scheduled start time if the robot is ready to execute the benchmark. If it is not ready:

- if the robot gets ready *before the scheduled end time for the run*, the run starts as soon as the robot is ready;
- if the robot gets ready *after the scheduled end time for the run*, the run does not take place at all.

The end of a run occurs when the scheduled end time is reached. The run ends earlier if any of the following events occur:

1. The door is back in the “locked” state while the robot is not on the *starting side*¹³ of the door assembly.
2. the robot enacts a *disqualifying behaviour* (see Section 8);
3. a team member requests the end of the benchmark.

The execution time used for the scoring (see Section 8) is always the actual duration of the run, i.e. from actual start time to actual end time. Values of the execution time are always between zero and the maximum timeout for Episode 10 (see Section 7.1). *The maximum value of the execution time is only available to robots that are ready at the scheduled start time.*

The following table recapitulates when the start and end of a run of Episode 10 occur:

The run starts...	The run ends...
between scheduled start time and scheduled end time, as soon as robot is ready	as soon as any of the following occurs: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● scheduled end time reached ● door is back in the “locked” state with robot not on starting side ● a disqualifying behaviour occurs ● team requests the end of the benchmark

For organisational reasons, scheduled times for the runs can be changed by the referees and republished after their first publication. When this occurs, the referees make sure that the teams involved by the changes are aware of them and, if possible, get feedback from the teams before finalising the changes.

7.1 Timeout

For Episode 10, timeout has a predefined maximum value, called **maximum timeout**. Maximum timeout for Episode 10 is **10 minutes**. The timeout value used while managing

¹³ See Section 4 for the definition of *starting side*.

benchmark runs is a percentage of the maximum timeout, increasing monotonically during the course of the benchmark according to the following mechanism:

- timeout is **50% of maximum timeout** until the robot reaches the **achievement threshold** defined in Section 8;
- timeout increases to **100% of the maximum timeout** as soon as the robot reaches the achievement threshold.

This variable timeout mechanism aims at preserving the interest of the public by ending early the benchmark runs where the robot is stuck, inactive or ineffective.

8. Score

The scoring mechanism used for Episode 10 is the same one used for the Task Benchmarks of the European Robotics League. As such, it is based on three sets: *Achievements*, *Penalised behaviours* and *Disqualifying behaviours*. Such sets are defined below.

Achievements

- **A1 - The robot approached the door.**
The achievement is awarded when two conditions are both true at the same time: (1) the robot is on the *starting side*¹⁴ of the door assembly and (2) there are at least one point of the robot and one point of the handle that are less than 1 m apart. This distance is assessed by the referees. As shown in the previous pictures, a circle can be drawn on the floor to determine when the robot is 1m away from the door, though it should not be too visible so robots can't use it to navigate the environment.
- **A2 - The robot touched the door handle.**
In order to get this achievement, the touched handle must be the one on the starting side of the door assembly. The handle is considered as "touched" if any part of the robot comes in physical contact with it.
- **A3 - The robot unlocked the door without human intervention.**
The robot gets this achievement when the door panel moves from the "closed" position of an amount incompatible with the locked state, according to the judgement of the referees. This achievement can be awarded only if no request to referees to intervene in the unlocking procedure has been issued by the robot's team, or if a request was issued but the robot unlocks the door by itself before a referee touches the handle or the door.
- **A4 - The robot passed through the door.**
The robot gets this achievement when it has moved through the door enough that there are no physical elements of the robot on the starting side of the door assembly. Reaching this state requires to open the door and pass through the aperture. The position of the door panel is not significant for this achievement.
- **A5 - The robot closed the door.**
This achievement is awarded if two conditions apply: (1) the robot is not on the starting side of the door assembly, and (2) the door is brought back against its own

¹⁴ See Section 4 for the definition of *starting side*.

frame by the robot so that its locking mechanism touches the corresponding plate on the door frame.

- **A6 - The robot locked the door.**

The robot gets this achievement when the locking mechanism of the door is back to the same “locked” state that it had at the start of the benchmark. This achievement is assigned only if, when this occurs, the robot is not on the *starting side* of the door assembly.

Penalising behaviours

- **PB1** - The robot hits any piece of the benchmark setup (e.g., a part of the door assembly) without inflicting damage¹⁵. An exception is made for the door cover panel and the door handle, which can be hit without penalty (provided that they do not get damaged).
- **PB2** - The robot exits the test area defined in Section 4 (even if it comes back in later).
- **PB3** - The unlocking action executed by a referee needs to be repeated (e.g., because the robot accidentally locks the door again).

An additional penalising behaviour is inflicted to the team every time the corresponding event occurs, even if the team has already been penalised for the very same behaviour.

In addition to the behaviours listed above, a request by the robot’s team to perform a *manual get-up* (see Section 6.1) counts as an additional penalising behaviour (**PB4**) for the robot.

Disqualifying behaviours

1. **DB1** - The robot hits a human (e.g., a referee)¹⁶.
2. **DB2** - The robot damages any piece of the benchmark setup.

Achievement threshold

Achievement A2 (The robot touched the door handle) is the **achievement threshold** for Episode 10. The achievement threshold is used to establish the timeout of the benchmark according to the mechanism described in Section 7.2.

8.1 Admission to the ranking

In order to be admitted to the ranking for Episode 10, a robot must have performed **at least 3 successful runs** of the benchmark, where a *successful run* is one during which the robot collected at least one achievement.

¹⁵ For the purpose of this rule, a “hit” is defined as a physical contact event where the robot applies forces sufficient to cause damage (even if no damage occurs).

¹⁶ For the purpose of this rule, a “hit” is defined as any touch that has the capability of inflicting damage to the human or their accessories (e.g., clothes), independently from the fact that a damage actually occurs.

Only teams whose robots are admitted to the ranking for Episode 10 receive a score, are included into the final ranking of teams, and can receive prizes or awards related to Episode 10.

8.2 Overall score

The competition is arranged in two stages: 1) Competition Days, 2) Final. The top 3 teams in the ranking of the Competition Days qualify for the final to be held in the last day of the competition. The final ranking for assigning the first, second and third place will be determined by the performance in the Final. During the competition days, several runs will be available to each team (let this number be M). Notice that M is the number of slots available for each team, it may differ from the actual number of performances of each team, if teams are not ready to attend some runs. During the Final, only one run will be performed.

Aggregate score of the Competition days. The aggregate score for each team for the M episodes performed during the Competition days will be determined according to the score system of the European Robotics League as follows:

- select the best N trials of the team
- determine the median of the scores of the N trials selected.

Let n be the position of the median in the ordered list of team scores, i.e., $n = (N + 1) / 2$ (when N is odd), then N (and consequently n) are determined according to the number of episodes scheduled M, according to the following table

M	N	n
6-9	5	3
10-12	7	4
13-15	9	5

In case of tie score for the access to the Final, the policy for tie breaking is described below. If such policy does not break the tie, all teams with the same score will enter the Final.

Tie breaker: In the case in which two teams have the same score the {maximum, minimum, last, average, cumulative} execution time over all the runs of the teams will break ties.

In case of tie score again, the rank will be the same. If teams with the same score are in the border limit to access the Final, all such teams will enter the Final.

9. Detailed instructions for referees

The information included in Section 6 (Procedure) and Section 8 (Score) should be sufficient to inform referees about -respectively- the events expected during the execution of the benchmark of Episode 10, and the aspects of such events that are significant with respect to the robot's score.

The only special indications that need to be provided are the following.

Check that the door assembly is in order.

Before each execution of the benchmark, the referees should make sure that the assembly works correctly. Special attention should be given to check the following aspects.

- **Horizontality.** As explained in Section 4, perfect horizontality of the door assembly is necessary to ensure perfect verticality of the rotation axis of the door panel. This, in turn, is needed to avoid gravity influencing the motion of the panel. A quick and precise way for the referee to check the verticality of the rotation axis is to perform motion checks with the door panel, by observing its motion when pushed. The key point is uniformity in panel motion over different parts of its angular range and while inverting the direction of motion.
- **Friction.** As explained in Section 4, the door hinges should have low friction, but not too low. The referee can check friction by ensuring that the door motion caused by a moderate push of the door panel is halted by friction within 30°-45°.

Referees should be aware that the physical interaction between robot and door assembly can compromise both horizontality and friction, so checks should be frequent.

Be alert against cheating.

If undetected, cheating is vastly superior to working in its reward-to-effort ratio. For this reason, a lack of checks against cheating means that it will likely occur, maybe in the next installment of Episode 10. To avoid this, referees should be alert, while avoiding being overly suspicious and therefore annoying to teams.

Given the way Episode 10 is structured, there are basically two types of cheating mechanisms, described below.

1. Before the execution of the benchmark. The robot is provided with *a priori* knowledge about how the door (e.g., its location, its opening direction). This cheating mechanism can be prevented by trying to limit the amount of information about the benchmark setup that a robot's team has access to, and by changing often that setup. For instance, the starting pose should be changed randomly at every execution of the benchmark.
2. During the execution of the benchmark. This cheating mechanism is based on the transmission of information from a team member to the robot. Especially dangerous is the case when a manual get-up occurs (see Section 6.1). This type of cheating can be prevented through vigilance and -if necessary- exemplary punishment inflicted to infringing teams.

The minimum requirement of Episode 10 on the number of referees is one. However, this is a suboptimal situation (especially when human intervention occurs) that is only acceptable when the setup of the benchmark allows the referee to move freely and quickly from one side to the other of the assembly.

A more effective configuration, and one that does not impose any constraint on the setup, is to have two referees, one on each side of the door assembly.

10. Detailed instructions for teams

The information included in Section 6 (Procedure) and Section 8 (Score) should be sufficient to inform teams about -respectively- what their robot and themselves are expected to do during the execution of the benchmark of Episode 10, what elements of such execution have an impact on their robot's score, and what is such impact.

11. Ethical issues

There are no ethical issues involved in Episode 10.

12. Safety procedures

The only safety procedures concerning the setup of Episode 10 concern the physical construction of the door assembly (see Section 4). As such, the only interested parties are the organizers of the competition, not the teams or visitors participating to it. Once installed, the door assembly does not require special safety procedures for usage (e.g., by team members during tests), since the procedure is completely equivalent to using a standard hinged door for indoor environments.

The only significant risk that the door assembly can pose to people (without considering those posed by standard doors, such as closing one's fingers in it) is its collapse, possibly due to being hit by a robot. The weight of the assembly is, in fact, sufficient to cause harm. However, provided that the assembly is installed correctly (i.e., as part of an existing and stable partition such as a wall) this risk is negligible¹⁷. Further minimisation of this risk is provided by the methods suggested to affix the assembly to the floor (see Section 4.4).

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¹⁷ Usage of the assembly by a robot large, heavy, powerful and quick-moving enough to cause the door assembly to topple notwithstanding its stabilising devices and the actions of the robot's own team is in theory conceivable. However, such a robot would represent such a large safety risk in itself that it would not be permitted to participate in the competition in the first place.

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Appendix A. Score sheet

Team: _____

Execution Time: _____

Trial number: _____

Achievements:

- The robot approached the door.
- The robot touched the door handle.
- The robot unlocked the door without human intervention.
- The robot passed through the door.
- The robot closed the door.
- The robot locked the door.

Penalizing behaviours:

- The robot hit a piece of the setup without damaging it. Number of hits: _____
[Note: non-damaging hits to door panel or handle should be ignored]
- The robot exited the test area. Number of exits: _____
- Door unlocking by a referee needed to be repeated. Number of repetitions: _____
- The robot required a manual get-up

Disqualifying behaviours:

- The robot hit a human.
- The robot damages any piece of the benchmark setup.

Notes:

Appendix B. Team information sheet

A Team Information Sheet is not required by Episode 10.

Episode 12

Fast delivery of emergency pills

Technical Committee

Francisco J. Perez Grau, CATEC, Spain

Antidio Viguria, CATEC, Spain

Ciro Potena, Sapienza University of Rome, Italy

Gianluca Bardaro, The Open University, UK

External expert: Davide Scaramuzza, University of Zurich, Switzerland

1. General Description

The aerial robot, or drone, must attend an emergency situation in which a first-aid kit needs to be delivered to a customer. The aerial robot must be able to fly autonomously to the customer location as fast as possible. The robot needs to detect and avoid possible obstacles on the way, and it must take into account that GPS coverage is not guaranteed.

2. Main scientific challenge

This episode aims at benchmarking some of the key functionalities required by an autonomous aerial robot to operate in indoor environments, such as localization, trajectory planning and obstacle detection and avoidance. A secondary functionality, while being basic for the episode success, is the ability to carry and deliver items in specific locations.

While drone-based delivery of items has been a popular topic in recent years with a lot of media attention [1], they are all assuming that the aerial platform will be operating in outdoor obstacle-free spaces. Outdoor operation for aerial robots based on Global Positioning System (GPS) can be generally assumed due to the existence of low-cost commercial products offering mature performances in a wide variety of applications [2]. Apart from logistic companies such as Amazon or UPS tackling the problem of parcel delivery using aerial robots, the European Robotics League (ERL) already proposed the challenge of drone-based delivery for emergency situations. In September 2017, the teams participating in ERL Emergency Major Tournament [3] showcased accurate and fast delivery capabilities in an outdoor realistic post-disaster scenario.

Despite this, emergencies may take place in any scenario, and there is no guarantee of a communication infrastructure or even access to GPS. Autonomous operation of drones in GPS-denied areas is being tackled by some drone vendors, but they show primary

positioning abilities that are not mature enough to be safely introduced in real and highly dynamic scenarios, or work reliably during long periods of time. In order to perform successfully in these environments, there is a need for additional competences in the robotic systems. In that sense, the aerial robotics research community has proposed coping with this issue in the form of competitions such as the European Robotics Challenges (EuRoC) [4], or the Autonomous Drone Racing [5] celebrated during the last editions of the IEEE International Conference on Intelligent Robots (IROS). Despite the fact that one of EuRoC teams addressed solving the problem of indoor GPS-free parcel delivery using aerial robots [6], this application was not initially proposed by the competition organizers for all teams. Nevertheless, both competitions have greatly helped to foster research developments in the field of autonomous navigation of drones in GPS-denied environments.

This episode wishes to push advanced developments in the context of Smart Cities and last-centimeter delivery, focusing on autonomous capabilities and indoor navigation for aerial robots, as these are important milestones to achieve for the emergency robotic systems of the future.

3. Platforms allowed

Only **Vertical Take-Off and Landing** (VTOL) multi-rotor aerial platforms using **electric power** will be allowed to participate, with a maximum diagonal size of **80 cm**.

The aerial robots must have a system to carry and deliver a small first-aid kit (see Section 4 for details).

The aerial robots must not rely on GPS signals for their autonomous operation, since the episode will take place in an indoor scenario.

The aerial robots must come with a **kill switch**, i.e. safety mechanism to immediately stop the motors at any moment. The kill switch will be under control of the team pilot, and it will be operated if safety of the operation is compromised (for example if the drone gets out of control or it crashes). NOTE: to prevent crashes, the pilot will be able to take manual control of the drone at any moment of any run, especially if a crash is imminent, without incurring in any penalisation (see scoring in Section 10).

4. Scenario Setup

The episode must take place inside a confined **flying arena**, defined as a delimited volume surrounded by walls and/or safety nets. A minimum ground floor area of 100 m² is expected for this episode. The height of the arena should be at least 3 meters. There should be at least 1 meter of separation between the safety nets and the public viewing area.

A specific point inside the arena must be defined as the **take-off location** for aerial robots, ideally close to one of the entry points to the flying arena. This position on the ground will be the origin of the coordinate system of the flying arena, i.e. takeoff=(X=0, Y=0, Z=0). This position must be marked on the floor with some kind of visible marker (e.g. stickers).

A second specific point in the arena must be defined as the **customer location** to which teams need to deliver the pills, opposite from the take-off location. This position will be measured in meters from the take-off position, i.e. customer=(X=TBD, Y=TBD, Z=0). This position must be marked on the floor with some kind of visible marker (e.g. stickers). Around this marker, concentric circles at 1m and 2m from the customer location must be also marked on the floor in order to assess the accuracy of delivery.

The customer can be represented by a **mannequin** placed in the customer location. The emergency pills can be represented by a small **first-aid kit**, for example [this one](#) (model 'Small, Helsinki') or any other that has a handle which teams could use so the aerial robot can grab it. The total weight of the package to be carried by the aerial robot must not exceed **200 grams**, to allow for small aerial platforms.

A small area for the team's **control station** must be set next to the take-off location, but outside the safety net. There must be an entry point to the flying arena nearby, so it is directly accessible for team members. The control station must have electric power for laptops and battery chargers, and two tables with minimum size of 2x1 m. Each table must be equipped with at least 4 chairs and 1 monitor (with power and HDMI cables).

Obstacles in the arena may be represented using physical objects usually present in a mall, such as lamps, palms, decorations, coffee machines, and so on. Banners from sponsors can be also included as obstacles.

There should be also obstacles on the ground, for example boxes, so the overall ground height is not always the same, and teams face true 3D navigation.

If possible, obstacles at height could be hung from the flying arena structure to represent more difficult obstacles, so drones should fly below them. These hung obstacles can also be sponsor banners. A rope mechanism could be attached to them so they are easily deployed at a specific height, and later removed by placing them at the very top of the flying arena.

Two main considerations for all the obstacles:

- The visual appearance of the obstacles should NOT be homogeneous (flat color), otherwise vision-based approaches will most likely fail.
- The minimum size of the obstacles in any dimension should be 20cm, to make sure onboard sensors can detect them (i.e. avoid the use of light poles).

As soon as a list of items is found by the local organizers and agreed with the technical committee of this episode, the detailed descriptions with pictures of the obstacles should be provided to the participating teams.

There can be two different obstacle dispositions, so teams face the delivery task with increasing difficulty:

- Easy: use only vertical obstacles between takeoff and customer locations. Aerial robots could reach the customer location by performing 2D navigation at a constant height.
- Hard: use vertical obstacles and also ground boxes and hung obstacles. Aerial robots are forced to perform true 3D navigation.

The disposition of obstacles in the arena must enable the navigation of the aerial robots between takeoff to customer locations, in terms of available free space and safety separation from such obstacles (at least 1 meter).

After offering the flying arena to teams for practicing during the first one or two days, we propose to organize the execution of the episode in two rounds of time slots (for each difficulty level), each one taking place in a different competition day. The idea is that teams are accumulating achievements during all three rounds, so the best team is the one that achieves the most difficult task (see score sheet for more details). During the Final the team will only face the Hard configuration of the obstacle, potentially with new unseen obstacles or a reduced available time to complete the objective.

Regarding the **variability** of the scenario, the take-off and customer locations will change depending on the difficulty level, to accommodate for two different path inside the cage. Between runs the obstacle configuration may change up to 2 meters, so we prevent teams to build the solution during practice using map-based or teach & replay approaches.

4.1 Scenario location

5. MK Data Hub Interaction

The Milton Keynes city hosting the competition is equipped with a data acquisition and management infrastructure (MK:DataHub) consisting of live sensors that reflect different aspects of the functionalities of the city (transport, environment, energy, water, etc.). The data gathered by the robots in this episode, such as the images, and potentially the estimated robot location, can be communicated automatically to the infrastructure to contribute to the smart city data platform.

Teams are notified before the competition by the competition organizers about the data and communication protocols if this interaction is required.

6. Procedure

This section describes the step by step procedure for a complete run of the episode. A single run consists of three phases that are executed sequentially without any interruptions. A robot can automatically continue to the next phase at any time if it is unable to execute or fully complete a phase.

Preparations and start

- A first-aid kit request with the location of a person in need, reaches a medical centre with medicine storage. The medical manager fills the first-aid kit ready to be delivered.
- The run begins, and the time starts, with the medical manager placing the first-aid kit to the take-off location.

Phase 1: Reach the customer location

- The aerial robot is positioned at the starting take-off location, and the first-aid kit is attached to it.
- The aerial robot request an estimated location of the person in need from the DH
- The aerial robot autonomously takes off towards the target location.
- During the navigation, the robot may need to detect and avoid different obstacles.

Phase 2: First-aid kit delivery

- The aerial robot autonomously lands nearby the customer location.
- The aerial robot detaches the first-aid kit.

Phase 3: Return to medical centre

- The aerial robot takes off again and navigates towards the initial take-off location.
- During the navigation, the robot may need to detect and avoid different obstacles.
- The aerial robot autonomously lands at the take-off location, ready for the next delivery.

7. Timing

The first day of the competition can be devoted to perform safety checks and robots compliance, and also for teams practice in the arena. Then for the actual competition, there will be two rounds of time slots for each team, with increasing difficulty according to the levels defined in Section 4, potentially organized in three different days.

Teams participation can be organized in time slots of **20 minutes**. The start time will follow a fixed, and pre-defined time schedule (no delays for any reason). The referees will also inform the participating team 10 minutes before the start of the time slot to place their robots and equipment in one of the tables of the control station area, just outside the flying arena. They must leave the other table free for the next participating team.

After the time slot of 20 minutes finishes, the referees will inform that the next participating team has 10 minutes to place their robots and equipment in the free table of the control station, while the team that has just participated has the same 10 minutes to pick up all their things. In this way, the organizers' time schedule can be set as **blocks of 30 minutes** (10 minutes of preparation + 20 minutes of competition). Depending on how many teams finally participate, these numbers can be subject to modifications.

Teams will be able to attempt the delivery as many times as they wish within the time slot, always starting from the take-off location. Take into account that the team score will not be the best attempt during the time slot, but an average of their top attempts (see Section 8). The time taken between the aerial robot take-off and landing on the take-off location after the delivery will also be recorded, as faster solutions are considered to be better in case of ties in the number of achievements.

It is a good idea to show in a big screen a time **countdown** of the time slot, so it is clear for all teams and also for the audience.

8. Score

The scoring mechanism used for this episode is the same one used for the Task Benchmarks of the European Robotics League. As such, it is based on three sets: *Achievements*, *Penalising behaviours* and *Disqualifying behaviours*. Apart from these sets, the whole time of the operation (take-off, delivery and landing back on the take-off area) will be recorded, to break ties between teams with the same amount of achievements.

Achievements

- Landing at the customer location with the specified accuracy (between 1 and 2 meters).
- Delivering the first-aid kit to the customer (i.e. leaving the first-aid kit within the specified accuracy).
- First-aid kit delivered within the first 5 minutes after the time slot starts.
- Landing back at the take-off location.
- Transmitting live images/video to the control station.
- Transmitting live robot position to the control station.

Penalising behaviours

- Manual interventions to the aerial robot in case it needs to be recovered from a failure (more details in Section 10).
- Hitting any of the structures in the flying arena (obstacles, safety net...).
- Getting closer than 1 m from the customer.

NOTE: battery changes are permitted.

Disqualifying behaviours

- The robot hits the customer.

- The robot damages the structures in the flying arena (obstacles, safety net...).
- The robot flies outside the flying arena.

8.1 Admission to the ranking

Each (scheduled) execution of the episode by a robot is called a **run** of the benchmark. The final score achieved by the robot depends on its performance over multiple runs of the benchmark.

In order to be admitted to the ranking, a robot must have performed **at least 3 successful runs** of the benchmark.

A *successful run* is one where the robot collected at least one achievement.

8.2 Overall score

The competition is arranged in two stages: 1) Competition Days, 2) Final. The top 3 teams in the ranking of the Competition Days qualify for the final to be held in the last day of the competition. The final ranking for assigning the first, second and third place will be determined by the performance in the Final. During the competition days, several runs will be available to each team (let this number be M). Notice that M is the number of slots available for each team, it may differ from the actual number of performances of each team, if teams are not ready to attend some runs. During the Final, only one run will be performed.

Aggregate score of the Competition days. The aggregate score for each team for the M episodes performed during the Competition days will be determined according to the score system of the European Robotics League as follows:

- select the best N trials of the team
- determine the median of the scores of the N trials selected.

Let n be the position of the median in the ordered list of team scores, i.e., $n = (N + 1) / 2$ (when N is odd), then N (and consequently n) are determined according to the number of episodes scheduled M , according to the following table

M	N	n
6-9	5	3
10-12	7	4
13-15	9	5

In case of tie score for the access to the Final, the policy for tie breaking is described below. If such policy does not break the tie, all teams with the same score will enter the Final.

Tie breaker: In the case in which two teams have the same score, the minimum execution time over all the runs of the teams will break ties.

In case of tie score again, the rank will be the same. If teams with the same score are in the border limit to access the Final, all such teams will enter the Final.

9. Detailed instructions for referees

There must be two referees for evaluating this episode. The referees/organizers must prepare a schedule to ensure an equal access of the arena to the participating teams for the setup and competition days.

BEFORE THE EPISODE

Safety checks

During the setup days, all robots will be checked by the referees for compliance. Only robots that successfully pass the safety checks will be able to participate in the competition.

Referees will check the safety mechanism of all the robots that intend to participate, which must be communicated by each team. A live demonstration is necessary for two aspects:

- activate the kill switch to automatically stop the motors.
- demonstrate flying skills of the team pilot: perform manual flights inside the flying arena following a specific figure, and recovery from autonomous to manual mode.

If the robot has other mechanical devices (e.g. a manipulator), their safety must be demonstrated as well.

Scenario setup

Referees must place obstacles in the arena according to the level of difficulty of the time slot. Before each time slot, referees must place the mannequin on the customer location. The customer location (relative meters in X and Y axis with respect to a specified center of the arena) will be set in the DataHub. Referees must communicate the participating team that they can start moving their robots and equipment to one of the tables of the control station 10 minutes prior to the time slot start.

After these 10 minutes, referees must take a first-aid kit, load it with the emergency pills to be delivered, and place it on the take-off location. At this point, referees can announce the start of the time slot and start the countdown of 20 minutes.

DURING THE EPISODE

Between runs within a time slot, the obstacles should be moved up to 2m around their current location to prevent teams from using training-based approaches.

Referees must take notes of all achievements and penalising behaviours using a score sheet per time slot. One of the referees, Referee 1, will be in charge of filling the score sheet and will stay at the control station with other team members. The other referee, Referee 2, must be able to move throughout the flying arena next to the team safety pilot, will check the aerial robot performance and other achievements, and will have a timer to record the time of each run. Ideally, both referees should have a direct communication link via walkie-talkie or similar.

Referee 1 will check live transmission of data at the ground station, among other achievements. Special attention must be put when scoring the obstacle detection and avoidance. Teams must show Referee 1 an online proof that obstacles are being

autonomously detected and avoided, for example explaining and showing the control station screen using the received images, highlighting the obstacle and/or the aerial robot trajectory.

Referee 2 will check if the aerial robot is running in autonomous or manual mode, will also check the proximity of the aerial robot when it lands near the customer location, as well as the actual delivery, and will also check if the aerial robot hits any obstacles or the safety net.

Battery changes of the aerial robot are allowed during the time slot without any penalisation.

The team safety pilot can avoid hitting obstacles by taking manual control of the robot, and this does not represent a penalising behaviour. Manual interventions incurring in penalising behaviours are defined as physically interacting with the aerial robot in order to continue the runs, for example due to: hitting any obstacles or the safety net, low battery so the aerial robot cannot return, malfunction if it does not respond to manual control, etc. Any manipulation of the aerial robot is allowed without penalisation only if it is done in the take-off location.

AFTER THE EPISODE

Referees must announce the end of the time slot, and let the following participating team 10 minutes to set up on the second table at the control station, while the current team has also these 10 minutes to pick up all their equipment.

Both referees must check the results of the participating team on the score sheet, and after agreement they must sign it. Then, they must show the results to the team leader in case there is any misunderstanding, and the team leader must sign it as well once discrepancies has been clarified, if any.

10. Detailed instructions for teams

BEFORE THE EPISODE

Safety checks

Teams may use different robots during different time slots. Teams must inform the referees of all robots that they intend to use, and each robot must pass a safety check before being used. Only robots that successfully pass the safety checks will be able to participate in the competition.

Teams will be asked to show the safety mechanism of their robots and to demonstrate their use. A live demonstration is necessary for:

- activate the kill switch to stop the motors.
- the team safety pilot must demonstrate his/her skills by flying in manual mode in the arena following a specific figure, and recovering from autonomous to manual mode.

If the robot has other mechanical devices (e.g. a manipulator), their safety must be demonstrated as well.

This check can be done at any time during the setup days. When teams are ready for an inspection, they can request one to the referees.

The team safety pilot must be clearly identified to the referees.

Scenario setup

A first-aid kit loaded with the emergency pills to be delivered will be provided by the referees at the take-off location. Teams have 10 minutes to set up in one of the tables of the control station, and must wait outside the flying arena for the start of their time slot. Teams may power up their equipment during the setup time, including the robot.

DURING THE EPISODE

The referees will indicate the start of the time slot. Then, the team is allowed to enter the flying arena. They can attach the first-aid kit to the aerial robot using whatever mechanism they have designed for the competition.

There will be one referee next to the control station, and another one next to the team safety pilot. Team members at the control station must clearly show if the obstacles are being detected and avoided in an autonomous manner, for example explaining and showing the control station screen using the received images, highlighting the obstacle and/or the aerial robot trajectory.

Battery changes of the aerial robot are allowed during the time slot without any penalisation.

The team safety pilot can avoid hitting obstacles by taking manual control of the robot, and this does not represent a penalising behaviour. Manual interventions incurring in penalising behaviours are defined as physically taking the aerial robot in order to continue the runs, for example due to: hitting any obstacles or the safety net, low battery so the aerial robot cannot return, malfunction if it does not respond to manual control, etc. Any manipulation of the aerial robot is allowed without penalisation only if it is done in the take-off location.

AFTER THE EPISODE

At the end of the time slot, the team leader will receive the score sheet from the referees in order to check the team performance, and after solving any discrepancy, he/she must sign it.

11. Ethical issues

There are no ethical issues involved in this episode.

12. Safety procedures

The only safety procedures concerning the setup of this episode concern the physical confinement of the flying arena. Safety nets must be robust to aerial robot propellers. There should be at least 1 meter of separation between the safety net conforming the flying arena and the public viewing area.

Aerial robots must only be operated inside this volume. Teams working with aerial robots outside the flying arena must remove the propellers, unless they are preparing for a time slot in the table next to the flying arena.

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Appendix A. Score sheet

Team Name: _____ Difficulty level (Easy/Medium/Hard):

Run Number: _____ Execution Time: _____

Referee 1: _____ Referee 2: _____

Achievements:

- The aerial robot autonomously lands within 1 and 2 meters from customer.
- The aerial robot autonomously delivers the first-aid kit within 1 and 2 meters from customer.
- The aerial robot delivers the first-aid kit within 5 minutes of the time slot.
- The aerial robot autonomously returns to the starting location and lands.
- The aerial robot transmits live images/video to the control station.
- The aerial robot transmits live position data to the control station.

Penalising behaviours:

- The aerial robot hits any of the structures in the flying arena. Number of hits: _____
- The aerial robot get closer than 1 m from the customer.
- The aerial robot needs manual intervention during a run.

- Battery changes are permitted.
- Flying in manual mode to recover the platform is allowed, the penalising behavior occurs when a team member physically takes the aerial robot.

Disqualifying behaviours:

- The robot hits the customer.
- The robot hits and damages structures in the arena.
- The robot flies outside the flying arena.

Notes:

Referee 1 signature:

Referee 2 signature:

Team leader signature:

Appendix B. Team information sheet

Not applicable.

